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ABBREVIATIONS

¹⁴ C:	Radiocarbon
aDNA	ancient DNA
BAM	Binary Alignment Map (file format)
BCE	Before Current Era
BCF	Binary Call Format (file format)
BED	Binary Editor Delete (file format)
BLOSUM	BLOCKS SUBstitution Matrix
CENIEH:	Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana
CH:	Cultural Heritage
CI	Confidence Interval
CIGAR	Concise Idiosyncratic Gapped Alignment Report
CRAM	Compressed Alignment Map (file format)
CSI	Coordinate-Sorted Index
DOT	Graphical Description Language (file format)
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
EnvS	Environmental Sciences
ES:	Earth Sciences
ESR	Electro Spin Resonance
EU:	European Union
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HapMap	haplotype map (international project)
HE:	Human Evolution
HS:	Heritage Science
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
HTS	High-throughput sequencing
Ma:	Million years
MAPQ	Mapping Quality
mtDNA	mitochondrial DNA
NGS	Next Generation Sequencing
NH:	Natural Heritage
OSL:	Optically Stimulated Luminescence
PED	Program Editor Delete (file format)
PH:	Physical Heritage
PHYLP:	PHYLogeny Inference Package (file format)
PMD	Post-Mortem Damage
PMG	Pagemaker Group File (file format)

PP:	Preparatory Phase
QA:	Quality Assurance
QC:	Quality Control
QC:	Quality Control
RMA	RealMedia audio (file format)
SAM	Sequence Alignment Map (file format)
SNP	Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
TMRCA	the most recent common ancestor
TNC:	Terrestrial Cosmogenic Nuclides
UCS:	Universal Chronology Service
VCF	Variant Call Format (file format)
VrE	Virtual Research Environment
WP:	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports about **Task 8.2 Feasibility studies**, which addresses the viability and manner of eventually incorporating new services, ensuring maximum efficiency for each interested beneficiary community. This aims at preparing E-RIHS for the delicate implementation phase of E-RIHS, tackling any potential flaws in its services. The feasibility studies concern different potential new services identified. Such potential new services address the common needs and integration of multiple HS communities. In this task small feasibility studies will address the viability and manner of eventually incorporating these services, ensuring maximum efficiency for each interested beneficiary community. This prepares E-RIHS for the delicate implementation of E-RIHS, tackling any potential flaws in its services.

All the subtasks listed below concern interoperability and cross-discipline applicability, mostly based on current best practices and involve no additional research.

Subtask 8.2.1 – Multilevel analysis: Identification, Digitisation and Reconstruction. Subtask leader: FORTH – Participants: ATOMKI(EK); FORTH(OFC_ADC); CENIEH; CNRS(IPANEMA); IPCHS; UCL(NTU)

This multidisciplinary Paleoanthropological and Bioarchaeological feasibility study concerned the design of an integrated pipeline involving different analytical techniques (e.g. Isotope, aDNA, Proteomics, Tomography, etc.) and their combination with advanced IT methods (e.g. 3D modelling) and the management of a combined repository.

Subtask 8.2.2 – Universal chronology service.

Subtask leader: CENIEH – Participants: ATOMKI; CNR(+INFN); CNRS; UCL(+SUERC)

The subject of the subtask concerns a feasibility study on the creation of a universal chronology service, comprising all relevant techniques used to date heritage (e.g. C14, luminescence, paleomagnetism). A ‘one door to knock on’ service helping to choose the most appropriate technique, laboratory and sampling. Users include museums, government and heritage-related organizations, art historians, archaeologists. A joint research program will be designed on the technique applicability, protocol homogenisation, training, etc.

Subtask 8.2.3 – Workflow in Digital Archaeology and Analytical Methods.

Subtask leader: CYI Participants: ATOMKI(HNM); CENIEH; DAI; DP; IAA; KIK-IRPA; UCL(NTU)

The feasibility study concerned the analysis and the design of the pipeline from field data documentation to site/artefact analysis, and how this process is recorded, performed and shared in a common knowledge repository while integrating analytical and digital methods.

Subtask 8.2.4 – Reference collections.

Subtask leader: RCE – Participants: ATOMKI(EK; HNM); CNR; FORTH; IPCHS; LNEC(+HERC); PIN; UCL

The subtask investigated how such collections may be mass-produced (RCE) and/or virtualised (PIN), to offer different scientific communities an easier availability of such important research tools and of guidelines for their use, contacting various scientific communities to analyse their needs.

Subtask 8.2.5 – Integration of scientific data with general heritage documentation.

Subtask leader: PIN Participants: ATOMKI(HNM); CNRS; FORTH; IPCHS; KIK-IRPA; RCE; UCL(+NG; SUERC)

The study analysed current best practices and design an integrated system where researchers can discover and use all the information concerning the subject of their study, regardless of its scientific or humanities origin.

Subtask 8.2.6 – Advanced materials for restoration.

Subtask leader: CNR(CSGI) Participants: CNR; CNRS(+C2RMF); DAI(RRL); FORTH; IPCHS; KIK- IRPA; LNEC(+HERC); UCL(NG)

The subtask analysed new solutions for the conservation, and the feasibility study concerns the design of an integrated pipeline involving different analytical tools and innovative materials for the definition of the best conservation procedures to ensure the best practice and maximum efficiency for the beneficiary community. Each subtask work is reported in the deliverable section numbered accordingly. References and appendices, when available, are included at the end of the related section.

SECTION 1 – MULTILEVEL ANALYSIS: IDENTIFICATION, DIGITISATION AND RECONSTRUCTION

1. Fundamentals of ancient DNA

The field of paleogenomics has grown rapidly over the last decade, as well as our understanding of the molecular structure and biochemistry of ancient DNA. During life, DNA is organized into very long, delicate strands, called chromosomes. After death, these long strands of DNA are no longer repaired and maintained by cellular enzymes and they begin to break down in predictable ways. Damage begins with sporadic DNA depurination – the loss of some adenine (A) and guanine (G) bases in the DNA molecule. This makes the DNA susceptible to nicking of the DNA backbone at these sites, which over time leads to fragmentation. Most DNA in a given archaeological sample is closer to 50 bp or less (Briggs *et al.* 2007).

In addition to depurination and fragmentation, aDNA also accumulates damage in the form of cytosine (C) deamination to uracil (U), which is incorrectly sequenced as a thymine (T). Such damage occurs orders of magnitude faster on the single-stranded overhangs at the ends of DNA fragments than in the double-stranded interiors, and this excess of damage at the ends of DNA fragments is used by dedicated software tools to authenticate ancient DNA. The ability to authenticate ancient DNA sequences using damage patterns is an enormous advantage of high-throughput sequencing (HTS) over previously used methods, such as Polymerase Chain Reaction, and filtering datasets to retain only damaged DNA is a powerful means of contamination removal that has been instrumental in recovering genomes from heavily contaminated samples, including from archaic hominins (Skoglund *et al.* 2014).

Many things have changed in ancient DNA laboratories over the past decade, but there are five major technological advancements that have truly transformed the field. First was the development of an extremely efficient protocol for recovering ultrashort DNA fragments from archaeological bone (Dabney *et al.* 2013). The second major advancement was the development of ancient DNA-optimized HTS library construction methods (e.g. Gansauge *et al.* 2017; Meyer & Kircher 2010) that refer to synthetic modifications made to DNA in order to become “readable”. The third important advancement was the development of uracil-DNA glycosylase (e.g. Rohland *et al.* 2015) protocols to selectively remove damaged sections of ancient DNA. The fourth major advancement was the development and adaptation of targeted enrichment methods (also known as DNA sequence capture) to selectively recover genomic regions of interest from ancient samples (e.g. Carpenter *et al.* 2013). Finally, the fifth major advancement was the development of HTS technologies that enabled the sequencing of not one but billions of DNA sequences simultaneously.

The effect of HTS on ancient DNA data analysis has also been profound. It is the sheer volume of genetic sequence data that has made the most difference. The benefit of having so much data is that very powerful statistical tools and inference methods can be applied to answer complex questions ranging from the population history of a continent to the virulence factors present in a historic pathogen.

2. Ancient DNA laboratories - Technical standards

Ancient DNA labs must be constructed under the highest technical standards and comply with the strict, international requirements of forensic labs. These include:

- Isolated building. The lab must be located in a building isolated from other laboratories that analyse DNA (DNA-free building), whereas all the construction materials must have non-biological origin.
- Restricted and supervised access. The access in the lab must be restricted only to the specialized staff.
- Appropriate room arrangement. The lab rooms must be properly designed and arranged following a gradient of cleanness in order to minimize the transportation of DNA from the environment to the cleanroom and the samples. For this, there must be gradual atmospheric pressure among the rooms.
- Ventilation via HEPA filters. The lab must be equipped with HEPA (High Efficiency Particulate Air) filters that are able to remove microparticles and allergens with high efficiency (99.97% of particles bigger than 300 nm).

- **Sterilization.** The lab rooms and its equipment must be sterilized after each use with specialized chemical agents and in everyday basis using an automatic UV-light mechanism.
- **Removal of pollutants and fumes.** Special mechanisms must be used to discard pollutants originated from sample drilling, as well as reagent fumes.
- **Exclusive equipment.** The equipment of the lab must be new and must be used exclusively to analyse ancient DNA.
- **Clothing.** All the clothing must consist of materials of non-biological origin. They include suits, masks, foot protection, boots, boot covers, sleeves, gloves, eye-shields *etc.* in order to avoid or minimize sample contamination with exogenous DNA.
- **Consumables.** All the consumables must be of forensic grade and stand for the highest quality and purity.
- **Sample handling – Protocols.** Both sample handling and protocols used must follow the standard and certified procedures of ancient DNA analysis, in order to minimize contamination and at the same time to maximize the potential of extracting the most reliable results and conclusions.

3. Ancient DNA applications

Research involving ancient DNA (aDNA) has experienced a true technological revolution in recent years through advances in the recovery of aDNA and, particularly, through applications of high-throughput sequencing (NGS). Formerly restricted to the analysis of only limited amounts of genetic information, aDNA studies have now progressed to whole-genome sequencing for an increasing number of ancient individuals and extinct species. Such advances have enabled the sequencing of specimens of up to several thousand years old. Novel methods of genomic analysis are able to shed light into various anthropological, paleontological, archaeological, and historical events. The aDNA applications are summarized below.

3.1. Determination of the genetic sex in individuals with non-diagnosable sex characteristics

The traditional identification of the sex in human archaeological samples is based on studying diagnosable sex-associated morphological characters. However, this is a difficult task in cases that an individual is represented by only a few osteoarcheological findings or in cases that the individual displays partial or mixed sex-related traits. The latter is common in individuals with osteological anomalies, as well as in children, which does not have developed distinguishable sex characters. The determination of the sex in ancient individuals is important for studying sex biases in historical processes and associations with specific sociocultural behaviours and archaeological context during the ancient times. A notable example is the study of Hedenstierna-Jonson *et al.* (2017), on an individual buried in a well-furnished warrior grave (Figure 1) in the Viking Age town of Birka, Sweden. The body was confirmed as a female Viking warrior despite previous studies that, based on the material and historical records, assigned the individuals to male sex.

Figure 1. Illustration of a Viking warrior grave.

3.2. Association between observed skeletal pathologies in ancient individuals and specific genetic diseases

Skeletal pathologies observed in the bones of excavated skeletal residues may be linked to one or a few specific genetic diseases. This can be done by locating (genotyping) disease-related polymorphisms in the individual’s genome. Usually, this practice requires DNA of good quality making it difficult to work with the poor quality and quantity of the ancient genetic material. However, targeted ancient DNA studies can provide indications of putative linked genetic diseases or syndromes and act as a complementary tool to further support or narrow down the findings of traditional palaeopathological methods, as in the whole-genome sequencing of the Atacama skeleton performed by Bhattacharya *et al.* (2018).

3.3 Tracing of ancient microbial pathogens and studying ancient epidemic events

The long-shared history between humans and infectious disease places ancient pathogen genomics within the interest of several fields such as microbiology, evolutionary biology, history and anthropology. The investigation of past infectious diseases has traditionally been conducted through palaeopathological assessment of ancient skeletal assemblages although this approach is limited by the fact that most acute infections do not leave visible traces on bone. Ancient DNA has brought molecular techniques to this study, providing a diachronic genetic perspective to infectious disease research. Since the published of the first ancient pathogen genome the field has expanded its directions to the in-depth study of infectious disease evolution, providing a unique resource for understanding human history. An example is Spyrou *et al.* (2019), investigating the phylogeography of the second plague pandemic (see also fig. 2 below).

Figure 2. The phylogenetic tree of *Yersinia pestis* focused on the second pandemic.

3.4. Reconstruction of specific phenotypic characters in ancient individuals

Most of the phenotypic characteristics are complex traits, making it difficult to identify associated genes responsible for their expression. However, externally visible characteristics such as eye, skin and hair colour have been studied genetically in depth, allowing their prediction from the genome of human samples that lack phenotypic information. This advance has been useful for studies dealing with the facial reconstruction of skulls found in archaeological excavations. Other phenotypic characters associated with specific genetic loci includes the lactose intolerance, the ABO blood group, and many more. An example of a facial

reconstruction study that incorporated ancient phenotype-associated genetic data is the one carried out by Hoole *et al.* (2018).

3.5. Study of the diet, public health and economies during the ancient times

Human evolution is closely linked to dietary changes and the development of new food-processing techniques. This is clearly observed in the transition from hunter-gatherer lifestyle to agriculture, which gave rise to cultivation of crops, animal husbandry, and permanent settlements. The more stable availability of food boosted the growth of Neolithic European populations. However, changes in diet had drawbacks for health, such as increased rates of caries. Added to this, permanent large settlements combined with the adoption of agriculture promoted the spread of density-dependent infectious diseases. Considering the impact of dietary habits on human evolution and health, the reconstruction of past human subsistence appears to be vital to our understanding of past societies, as in Sjøe *et al.* (2018).

3.6. Assignment of individuals to population genetic groups based on their matrilineal or patrilineal ancestry

Human DNA ancestry studies have permitted to assign humans in unilinear genealogical groups, called haplogroups, sharing one common ancestor at one given point in prehistory. In human genetics, the most commonly studied unilinear molecular markers are the Y-chromosome (Y-DNA) and the mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA), each of which can be used to define genetic populations. Y-DNA is passed solely along the patrilineal line, from father to son, whereas mtDNA is passed down the matrilineal line, from mother to offspring of both sexes. Ancient DNA recovered from excavated human remains can also be used to assign the individual to population genetic groups and also recover polymorphisms that no longer exists, see e.g. Lazaridis *et al.* (2017) who recovered genome-wide data from ancient individuals, including Minoans from Crete and Mycenaeans from the mainland Greece.

3.7. Palaeogenomics of extinct species and molecular identification of the species

Animal palaeogenomics focus on the study of extinct taxa aiming to unravel their evolutionary history via comparative genomic analysis between ancestor and descendant taxa. This application is especially intriguing for discovering extinct lineages of contemporary species. Thus, although the analyses are performed for a single specimen, usually it represents an entire taxon (e.g. lineage, subspecies, and species). In cases of ancient findings of unknown animal species aDNA analysis contributes also to the molecular identification of the species. The latter is quite helpful in cases of isolated findings (e.g. a single tooth) that lack diagnosable skeletal characters of taxonomic identification and in cases that the resolution of the diagnosable morphological characters is not high enough to distinguish closely related taxa. One such example is in Min-Shan Ko *et al.* (2018).

3.8. Inferring the kinship among a group of individuals and the study of relatedness issues

It is quite common in archaeology to excavate tombs that contain multiple individuals or to find burials closely located or in the same cemetery precinct. In such cases the first hypothesis that is tested is if the individuals found are related to each or not. In many cases and especially in those that the archaeological and the anthropological context is not enough, the kinship is hard to be inferred. Ancient DNA can be utilized in such studies to help determine not only if the individuals are related to each other, but also to infer the degree of their relationship (i.e. parent – child, full-siblings, half-siblings etc.). Furthermore, aDNA based kinship estimation can be implemented for genetic identification of an unknown buried individual, whose (living or not) relatives are known, as in the study by Fernandes *et al.* (2017).

3.9. Unravelling the origin of human species and the relationships among the extinct members of the human genus

The complete sequencing of archaic and modern human genomes has revolutionized the study of human history and evolution. The story of Neanderthal and Denisovan origins has developed rapidly during the past decades. High coverage and fragmentary genome data have yielded powerful insights about the diversity of these ancient groups and their legacy of genetic introgression into recent humans. These archaic populations share a deep common history, and individual genomes record a history of high inbreeding and low gene flow

across their ancient geographic ranges. A simplified model of admixture history between archaic and anatomically modern human populations was presented by Wolfand Akey (2018).

3.10. Studying the relationships, admixture and dispersal events among ancient populations

Total genomic sequencing of ancient DNA from human excavation findings can provide unique information about the origin and movements of past populations of humans (and other non-human animals). Using appropriate bioinformatics tools, ancient DNA studies focus on the relationships amongst populations seeking also genetic ‘signatures’ that indicate specific demographic events. A case study in this topic is Martiniano *et al.* (2016).

3.11. Continuity and genetic relationships between ancient and contemporary human populations

By comparing DNA sequences obtained from archaeological human remains from a specific geographic area with DNA sequences retrieved from present-day people that live nowadays in the same area is one of the main focus of ancient DNA study in order to test continuity hypothesis, population turn-over cases and colonization. This was studied e.g. in Rodríguez-Varela *et al.* (2017) generated the first genome-wide sequence data from eleven archaeological Guanche individuals originating from Gran Canaria and Tenerife.

3.12. Evidence of adaptation and natural selection in human traits

Ancient DNA makes it possible to observe natural selection directly by analysing samples from populations before, during and after adaptation events. While indirect evidence of adaptation can be detected in patterns of genetic variation in present-day people, these patterns are only echoes of past events, which are difficult to date and interpret, and are often confounded by neutral processes. Ancient DNA provides a direct way to study these patterns, and it is considered a transformative technology for studies of selection, as for instance in Mathieson *et al.* (2015).

3.13. Genetic manifestation of domestication on animals and plants

New scientific knowledge generated with paleogenomic methods is rapidly changing our understanding of the genetic basis of animal and plant domestication and the origins and dispersal of livestock and companion animals. These techniques have been particularly informative in revealing high-resolution patterns of artificial and natural selection and evidence for significant admixture between early domestic animal and plant populations and their wild congeners. Among others, Ottoni *et al.* (2017) studying the cat’s worldwide conquest from the Neolithic period to Middle Ages and later.

Figure 3. Spatio-temporal representation of cat maternal genealogies (left). Alleles determining the phenotypic variation in the shape of tabby patterns (right).

4. The need of Ancient DNA Services

One of the primary challenges of paleogenomics research is that highly specialized facilities, resources and skills are required. Ancient DNA laboratories are specifically designed to meet rigorous cleanroom standards that simply cannot be met in an ordinary genetics laboratory. When ancient DNA research is attempted outside of lab space specifically designed for this purpose, contamination and false positives are very likely. Ancient DNA is most vulnerable to laboratory contamination during DNA extraction and high-throughput sequencing library steps prior to indexing PCR amplification. Subsequent post-PCR steps can be performed in more typical genetics labs, but the initial steps must be performed in a dedicated ancient DNA laboratory.

Paleogenomics research also requires significant investment in computational resources for both data storage and analysis. Competency in programming languages and a background in evolutionary theory and statistical analysis are critical skills for any downstream analysis or data interpretation.

5. Ancient DNA Wetlab Services

5.1 DNA Extraction

Ancient DNA can be successfully recovered from a wide range of bioarcheological materials, including bone, teeth, desiccated and mummified soft tissues, paleofeces, hair, dental calculus, seeds and other plant material, cultural objects, and sediments, among others. Efficient protocols for recovering ultrashort DNA fragments from archaeological sources have been developed.

5.2 High-throughput sequencing library construction

Library refers to the end product of a suite of synthetic modifications made to the DNA in order to make it “readable” by sequencing instruments. Optimized for ancient DNA library construction protocols have been developed including robust protocols for both double-stranded and single-stranded DNA libraries, as well as the use of single- or dual-indexing to perform parallel sequencing of multiple samples in the same run. Quick and easy, double-stranded library preps are suitable for most archaeological samples with average to good preservation, whereas single-stranded library preps are used to recover DNA from marginal samples from warm climates or deep time.

5.3 Targeted enrichment (DNA sequence capture)

This service includes methods to selectively recover genomic regions of interest from ancient samples. The goal of capture is to “fish-out” desired DNA sequences from a sea of unwanted (usually environmental) DNA so that less sequencing effort and cost is needed to obtain the desired genetic information.

6. Contribution of ancient DNA analysis in the pipeline of ancient human facial reconstruction.

The pipeline of the methods preceding the facial reconstruction of an ancient human includes the excavation study, the osteological analysis, the ancient DNA analysis, the computed-tomography scan (or use of other similar method), the isotopic analysis, and the digitization analysis. Here, the contribution of ancient DNA analysis is presented.

Ancient DNA can inform about visible and non-visible phenotypic characteristics. The later, such as blood type have zero value for the reconstruction. The former, includes mostly characteristics related to pigmentation, such as the colour of hair, eyes and skin, but may also include other types, such as hair morphology and presence of freckles. This type of characteristics is genetically linked to specific genetic loci

and thus, they can be determined by studying these genetic loci and interpreting the genetic information they carry. An example of this type of application is presented in Section 2 of the present document and the bioinformatics tools that are needed are given in the list of Section 6.

Ancient DNA can also inform about the genetic sex of the individual in order to confirm the conclusion of the osteological analysis or in cases that the individual has mixed sexual characteristics (*e.g.* a child) it can be the only tool that can be used to infer the sex of the ancient person.

Finally, Ancient DNA can also be used to acquire information about the ancestry of an ancient human and depending on how old is the excavation sample dated, the result can be used to compare with a contemporary group of humans that are the most closely ancestors to the sample and obtain some information regarding the facial characteristics by them.

7. Ancient DNA Bioinformatics Services

There are numerous analyses that can be performed by utilizing ancient DNA data generated with Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) platforms. Most analyses are similar to those conducted using NGS data from modern samples. However, they require either the use of software tools dedicated to aDNA data because they take into account specific characteristics of the aDNA sequences, or the selection of different parameters when using software tools that handle both modern and ancient DNA data. In this section different analyses are summarized that can be conducted during an archaeogenetics analyses. They can be assigned to different major groups including the initial analyses that must be performed in order to ensure that the data are sufficient and of appropriate quality, the intermediate analyses associated with the nature of the ancient DNA data, and finally the more advanced analyses that result in providing insights into various scientific questions.

A list of Analysis Software Tools is included in Appendix 1.

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Appendix – List of aDNA Analysis Software Tools

Analyses Overview

1. *Sequencing data quality metrics*
2. *Trimming of adapters and raw sequence data filtering*
3. *Filtered sequencing data quality metrics*
4. *Mapping to reference genome and mapping statistics generation*
5. *Local realignment of indels*
6. *Damage estimation*
7. *Contamination estimation based on mtDNA*
8. *Genetic sex estimation*
9. *Contamination estimation based on chromosome X in males*
10. *Contamination removal*
11. *Matrilineal ancestry determination (Mitochondrion)*
12. *Patrilineal ancestry determination (Y chromosome)*
13. *Kinship analysis*
14. *Calling or imputing of selected SNPs associated with phenotypes or genetic diseases*
15. *Population clustering analysis*
16. *Admixture analysis*
17. *Phylogenetic analysis*
18. *Metagenomics analysis*

In some cases, many different tools have been developed that perform the same or a similar task associated to the aforementioned analyses. Because of this, a representative software tool is presented in the next section and some alternatives are mentioned. The installing dependencies should be searched for in the software manuals.

FastQC

Associated with analyses: 1, 3, and optionally 4

Summary

FastQC aims to provide a simple way to do some quality control checks on raw sequence data coming from high throughput sequencing platforms. It provides a modular set of analyses which the user can use to give a quick impression of whether the data have any problems of which the user should be aware before doing any further analysis.

Input: BAM, SAM or FastQ file (may be compressed with GZip).

Output: Summary graphs and tables in an HTML based permanent report.

Most important command line options (see the manual for the complete list)

-f --format

Bypasses the normal sequence file format detection and forces the program to use the specified format. Valid formats are bam, sam, bam_mapped, sam_mapped and fastq.

-t --threads

Specifies the number of files which can be processed simultaneously. Each thread will be allocated 250MB of memory so you shouldn't run more threads than your available memory will cope with, and not more than 6 threads on a 32 bit machine.

-o --outdir

Create all output files in the specified output directory. Please note that this directory must exist as the program will not create it. If this option is not set then the output file for each sequence file is created in the same directory as the sequence file which was processed.

Download links: [babraham page](#), [github](#)

Manual links: [manpage](#), [babraham page](#), [dnacore page](#)

Tutorial links: [youtube](#), [babraham page](#)

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [MultiQC](#), [FaQCs](#), more can be found [here](#)

AdapterRemoval

Associated with analyses: 2

Summary

AdapterRemoval searches for and removes remnant adapter sequences from High-Throughput Sequencing (HTS) data and (optionally) trims low quality bases from the 3' end of reads following adapter removal. AdapterRemoval can analyze both single end and paired end data, and can be used to merge overlapping paired-ended reads into (longer) consensus sequences. Additionally, AdapterRemoval can construct a consensus adapter sequence for paired-ended reads, if which this information is not available.

Input: FastQ file (optionally GZipped)

Output: Table (text file) with adapter trimming statistics, Filtered/Trimmed reads (FastQ file)

Most important command line options (see the manual for the complete list)

--trimns

Trim consecutive Ns from the 5' and 3' termini. If quality trimming is also enabled (--trimqualities), then stretches of mixed low-quality bases and/or Ns are trimmed.

--minquality minimum

Set the threshold for trimming low quality bases using --trimqualities and --trimwindows.

--trimqualities

Trim consecutive stretches of low quality bases (threshold set by --minquality) from the 5' and 3' termini. If trimming of Ns is also enabled (--trimns), then stretches of mixed low-quality bases and Ns are trimmed.

--minlength length

Reads shorter than this length are discarded following trimming.

Download links: [github](#)

Manual links: [readthedocs](#)

Tutorial links: [readthedocs](#)

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [Trimmomatic](#), [Cutadapt](#), [IeeHom](#) more can be found [here](#)

Seqtk

Associated with analyses: 2 and optionally 15

Summary

Seqtk is a fast and lightweight tool for processing sequences in the FASTA or FASTQ format. It seamlessly parses both FASTA and FASTQ files which can also be optionally compressed by gzip. Seqtk can convert FastQ data to FastA format, reverse complement FastA/Q, extract sequences with names in a given file (one sequence name per line), extract sequences in regions listed in a given file, mask regions to lowercases, trim low-quality bases from both ends using the Phred algorithm, trim a certain number of base pairs from the left end of each read and a certain number from the right end.

Input: FastQ (optionally GZipped) or FastA file

Output: Processed sequences in FastQ (optionally GZipped) or FastA file

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

seq -a

Common transformation of FASTA/Q.

seq -r

Reverse complement of FASTA/Q.

subseq

Extract sequences with names in file name.lst, one sequence name per line

sample

Subsample sequences.

trimfq (-b; -e)

Trim low-quality bases from both ends using the Phred algorithm. Available options (-b/-e) for trimming bases from read ends.

Download links: [github](#)

Manual links: [github](#)

Tutorial links: [Liang-Bo page](#)

Publication links: Not-published in journal.

Other similar software tools: [SeqKit](#)

BWA

Associated with analyses: 4 and optionally 15

Summary

BWA is a software package for mapping low-divergent sequences against a large reference genome, such as the human genome. It consists of three algorithms: BWA-backtrack, BWA-SW and BWA-MEM. The first algorithm is designed for Illumina sequence reads up to 100bp, while the rest two for longer sequences ranged from 70bp to 1Mbp. BWA-MEM and BWA-SW share similar features such as long-read support and split alignment, but BWA-MEM, which is the latest, is generally recommended for high-quality queries as it is faster and more accurate. BWA-MEM also has better performance than BWA-backtrack for 70-100bp Illumina reads. For all the algorithms, BWA first needs to construct the FM-index for the reference genome (the index command).

Input: Filtered reads in FastQ (optionally GZipped) file, Reference Genome in FastA file

Output: SAM file

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

index

Index database sequences (reference genome) in the FASTA format.

aln (-l)

Find the sequence alignment (SA) coordinates of the input reads. If -l is used: take the first INT subsequence as seed. If INT is larger than the query sequence, seeding will be disabled.

samse (or sampe)

Generate alignments in the SAM format given single-end (or paired-end) reads. Repetitive hits will be randomly chosen.

Download links: [github](#)

Manual links: [sourceforge](#)

Tutorial links: [Elementolab page](#)

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [Bowtie](#)

SAMtools

Associated with analyses: 4, 8, 10, 12, 13 and optionally 15

Summary

SAMtools implements various utilities for post-processing alignments in the SAM format, such as indexing, variant caller and alignment viewer, and thus provides universal tools for processing read alignments.

Input: SAM/BAM/CRAM file, , Reference genome (FastA file).

Output: BAM (optionally compressed)/CRAM file

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

view

With no options or regions specified, prints all alignments in the specified input alignment file to standard output (with no header). Many filtering and output format options.

sort

Sort alignments by leftmost coordinates, or by read name when -n is used. An appropriate @HD-SO sort order header tag will be added or an existing one updated if necessary.

fixmate

Fill in mate coordinates, ISIZE and mate related flags from a name-sorted alignment.

markdup (-r)

Mark duplicate alignments from a coordinate sorted file that has been run through fixmate. The option -r removes duplicates.

index

Index a coordinate-sorted BAM or CRAM file for fast random access.

idxstats

Retrieve and print stats in the index file corresponding to the input file.

Download links: [htslib page](#)

Manual links: [htslib page](#)

Tutorial links: several examples are given in the manual.

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [sambamba](#), [Picard](#)

Qualimap

Associated with analyses: 4

Summary

Qualimap is a platform-independent application written in Java and R that provides both a Graphical User Interface (GUI) and a command-line interface to facilitate the quality control of alignment sequencing data and its derivatives like feature counts. Qualimap examines sequencing alignment data in SAM/BAM files according to the features of the mapped reads and provides an overall view of the data that helps to detect biases in the sequencing and/or mapping of the data and eases decision-making for further analysis.

Input: SAM/BAM file

Output: report (Text and PDF files)

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

`bamqc`

Perform Quality Control (QC).

`bamqc -bam`

Input mapping file in BAM format.

`bamqc -nt`

Number of threads.

`bamqc -outformat`

Format of the output report (PDF or HTML).

`bamqc -ip`

Activate this option to collect statistics of overlapping paired-end reads.

`multi-bamqc`

Perform multi-sample BAM QC.

Download links: [qualimap page](#)

Manual links: [qualimap page](#)

Tutorial links: detailed step-by-step usage is given in the manual.

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [SAMStat](#)

Tablet

Associated with analyses: 4

Summary

Tablet is a lightweight, high-performance graphical viewer and navigator for next generation sequence assemblies and alignments. Tablet features include high-performance visualization and data navigation; display of reads in both packed and stacked formats; search and locate reads by name or subsequence across entire data sets; paired end visualization support; CIGAR support within SAM/BAM for showing insertions, deletions, clipping events, etc.; entire-contig overviews, showing data layout or coverage information. Tablet's visualizations are split into several areas. The main display provides a visualization of a single contig at a time, with reads aligned against their consensus sequence. Tablet will lay out the data in either packed (showing as many reads per line as possible without overlap) or stacked (showing one read per line) formats. The read data is supplemented with the consensus sequence and its quality scores, coverage information (per base) and up to six consensus to protein translations (3 reading frames, forward and reverse). More specifically for BAM input, Tablet supports BAM indexed query for visualizing large alignments. Indexed query makes it possible to support visualization of alignments in the hundreds of gigabytes of data on disk. In this view, Tablet displays subsets of the data at a time; while still providing the ability to move easily through - and jump to any point within - the dataset. The visualization of indexed BAM data is subtly different from the visualization of other assembly formats. While most of the display remains the same, there are a few extra display components to aid the visualization - and navigation - of indexed BAM data.

Input: SAM, BAM, FASTA, and FASTQ file

Output: options to export an image (PMG) or a coverage summary.

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

This software tool is a visualizer. Thus, the command line can be used mostly to open the graphical user interface (GUI).

Download links: [Tablet page](#)

Manual links: [readthedocs page](#)

Tutorial links: [Tablet page](#)

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [IGV](#)

PreSeq

Associated with analyses: 4

Summary

The preseq package is aimed at predicting and estimating the complexity of a genomic sequencing library, equivalent to predicting and estimating the number of redundant reads from a given sequencing depth and how many will be expected from additional sequencing using an initial sequencing experiment. The estimates can then be used to examine the utility of further sequencing, optimize the sequencing depth, or to screen multiple libraries to avoid low complexity samples.

Input: BAM or BED file

Output: Tables with sequencing yield estimates (Text).

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

c_curve

c curve is used to compute the expected complexity curve of a mapped read file by subsampling smaller experiments without replacement and counting the distinct reads. Output is a text file with two columns. The first gives the total number of reads and the second the corresponding number of distinct reads.

lc_extrap

lc_extrap is used to generate the expected yield for theoretical larger experiments and bounds on the number of distinct reads in the library and the associated confidence intervals, which is computed by bootstrapping the observed duplicate counts histogram. Output is a text file with four columns. The first is the total number of reads, second gives the corresponding average expected number of distinct reads, and the third and fourth give the lower and upper limits of the confidence interval. Specifying verbose will print out the counts histogram of the input file.

Download links: [Preseq page](#)

Manual links: [Preseq page](#)

Tutorial links: several examples are given in the manual.

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: None

Picard

Associated with analyses: 5

Summary

Picard is a set of command line tools for manipulating high-throughput sequencing (HTS) data and formats such as SAM/BAM/CRAM and VCF. Here, Picard is used mostly for changing the header of the SAM/BAM files in order to be compatible with the GATK software (next section).

Input: SAM / BAM / VCF

Output: options to export an image (PMG) or a coverage summary.

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

AddOrReplaceReadGroups

Replace read groups in a BAM file. This tool enables the user to replace all read groups in the input file with a single new read group and assign all reads to this read group in the output BAM file.

Download links: [broadinstitute](#) page

Manual links: [broadinstitute](#) page

Tutorial links: several examples are given in the manual.

Publication links: Not-published in journal

Other similar software tools: [SAMtools](#)

GATK

Associated with analyses: 5 (other tools than those specified below: 4 and 14)

Summary

GATK is a collection of command-line tools for analyzing high-throughput sequencing data with a primary focus on variant discovery. The tools can be used individually or chained together into complete workflows. Here, the focal tools of this collection are the *RealignerTargetCreator* and the *IndelRealigner*. The first defines the intervals to target for local realignment, whereas the second performs local realignment of reads around indels. The local realignment process is designed to locally realign reads such that the number of mismatching bases is minimized across all the reads. In general, a large percent of regions requiring local realignment are due to the presence of an insertion or deletion (indels) in the individual's genome with respect to the reference genome. Such alignment artifacts result in many bases mismatching the reference near the misalignment, which are easily mistaken as SNPs. Moreover, since read mapping algorithms operate on each read independently, it is impossible to place reads on the reference genome such that mismatches are minimized across all reads. Consequently, even when some reads are correctly mapped with indels, reads covering the indel near just the start or end of the read are often incorrectly mapped with respect the true indel, also requiring realignment. Local realignment serves to transform regions with misalignments due to indels into clean reads containing a consensus indel suitable for standard variant discovery approaches.

Input: BAM file, Reference genome (FastA file).

Output: *RealignerTargetCreator* exports a list (Text) of target intervals that is passed to *IndelRealigner*. The latter exports a realigned version of the input BAM file.

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

-T *RealignerTargetCreator*

Use of the *RealignerTargetCreator* tool. Basic options regarding input and output files.

-T *IndelRealigner*

Use of the *IndelRealigner* tool. Basic options regarding input and output files.

Download links: [broadinstitute](#) page

Manual links: [broadinstitute](#) page (general), : [broadinstitute](#) page (specific tools)

Tutorial links: [RealignerTargetCreator](#), [IndelRealigner](#), for other GATK tools see [here](#)

Publication links: [PubMed1](#), [PubMed2](#), [PubMed3](#)

Other similar software tools: [ABRA](#)

mapDamage

Associated with analyses: 6

Summary

mapDamage is a computational framework written in Python and R, which tracks and quantifies DNA damage patterns (nucleotide misincorporation and fragmentation patterns) among ancient DNA sequencing reads generated by Next-Generation Sequencing platforms mapped against a reference genome. The main feature of the latest version is the approximate Bayesian estimation of damage parameters. The program can be optionally used to rescale quality scores of likely damaged positions in the reads. A new BAM file is constructed by downscaling quality values for misincorporations likely due to ancient DNA damage according to their initial qualities, position in reads and damage patterns.

Input: NGS reads in SAM/BAM file and reference genome in FastA file.

Output: Tables (Text) and Plots (PDF) with the estimated damage patterns. Optionally, a new BAM file with rescaled reads.

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

--merge-reference-sequences

Ignore reference sequence names when tabulating reads (using '*' instead). Useful for alignments with a large number of reference sequences, which may otherwise result in excessive memory or disk usage due to the number of tables generated.

-Q

Minimum base quality Phred score considered, Phred-33 assumed.

--rescale

Rescale the quality scores in the BAM file using the output from the statistical estimation.

Download links: [Github page](#)

Manual links: [mapDamage page](#)

Tutorial links: several examples are given in the manual.

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [PMDtools](#)

schmutzi

Associated with analyses: 7 and optionally 11.

Summary

Schmutzi is a set of programs aimed at ancient DNA data that can a) estimate contamination based on deamination patterns alone, b) call a mitochondrial consensus for the endogenous genome; this consensus calls takes into account contamination and deamination, c) estimate mitochondrial contamination and identify the most likely contaminant from a set.

Input: sorted-indexed-fillmd/calmd BAM file, Reference genome (FastA file).

Output: Tables with contamination estimations (Text). Optionally, the endogenous mtDNA consensus sequence (FastA file).

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

contDeam.pl

Allows for the estimation of endogenous deamination and subsequent contamination estimate using those. Assuming that the contaminant is not deaminated, it will measure rates of deamination for the endogenous material and provide a rough contamination estimate.

contDeam.pl --lengthDeam

the number of bp (at the read ends) considered to be deaminated

schmutzi.pl

Performs two tasks: 1) Call an endogenous consensus. 2) Using the consensus called in 1) and a set of known contaminants, computes the contamination rate for entry in this set. Returns the most likely contaminant with its corresponding rate.

schmutzi.pl --uselength

Use length of the molecules as well

Download links: [Github page](#)

Manual links: README file in Github page

Tutorial links: [GAWorkshop page](#) and Github page

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: ContaMix (not published; available upon request from [Johnson Lab](#))

ANGSD

Associated with analyses: 7 and 11.

Summary

ANGSD is a software for analyzing next generation sequencing data. The software can handle a number of different input types from mapped reads to imputed genotype probabilities. Most methods take genotype uncertainty into account instead of basing the analysis on called genotypes. This is especially useful for low and medium depth data. The software is written in C++ and has been used on large sample sizes. Here, we use ANGSD mostly for contamination estimation, but only for chromosomes that exists in one gene copy (e.g. chrX for males). This method requires a list of polymorphic sites along with their frequency and we also recommend to discard regions with low mappability.

Input: BAM file

Output: Table with contamination estimation (Text).

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

-doCounts

Calculate various counts statistics (Count the number A,C,G,T. All sites, All samples)

-r

Provide which part of the chromosome X we should considered as single-copy. The pseudo-autosomal region should be not included.

-iCounts

Generates a binary count file for chrX (Internal format for dumping binary single chrs
contamination

Performs the actual contamination estimation

Download links: [Github page](#)

Manual links: [ANGSD page](#)

Tutorial links: [GAWorkshop page](#)

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [dice](#)

Ry_compute.py

Associated with analyses: 8

Summary

This script constitutes a simple strategy that makes use of all the relevant information in alignments to both the sex chromosomes, leveraging the power of shotgun sequencing without the need for detailed filtering of the Y-chromosomal reference sequence. Sex assignment (where samples with no evidence for the presence of a Y chromosome are denoted 'female' and samples with evidence of a Y chromosome are denoted 'male') is performed by computing the number of alignments to the Y chromosome (n_Y) as a fraction of the total number of alignments to both sex chromosomes ($n_X + n_Y$) denoted as R_Y where $R_Y = n_Y / (n_X + n_Y)$. Specifically, a sample is assigned as female if its confidence interval (CI) upper bound for R_Y is lower than 0.016. A sample is assigned as male if its R_Y CI lower bound is higher than 0.075.

Input: SAM/BAM file

Output: Table with sex determination results (Text).

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

This software tool is a script that needs the input to be fed using the *SAMtools* subcommand *view*. The most important *SAMtools view* parameter is:

-q

Discards reads with mapping quality (MAPQ) < 30.

Download links: Supplementary data of publication.

Manual links: Inside the script.

Tutorial links: Inside the script.

Publication links: [ScienceDirect](#)

Other similar software tools: [Rx_identifier.R](#) (Supplementary Info script), [SEXCMD](#)

PMDtools

Associated with analyses: 10 and optionally 6

Summary

PMDtools implements a likelihood framework incorporating postmortem damage (PMD), base quality scores and biological polymorphism to identify degraded DNA sequences that are unlikely to originate from modern contamination. Using the model, each sequence is assigned a PMD score, for which positive values indicate support for the sequence being genuinely ancient.

Input: SAM (fed by SAMtools using a pipe) with an MD tag.

Output: Contamination-free BAM file, optionally damage graphs (PDF)

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

--threshold

Restrict to sequences with a PMD score above this threshold.

--platypus

Compute deamination-derived damage patterns separating CpG and non-CpG sites.

--deamination

Output base frequencies in the read at positions where there are C or G in the reference.

--CpG

Only use Cs and Gs in CpG context

-q (-m)

Only process bases with base (or mapping; -m) quality at least this great.

--stats

Output summarizing statistics.

Download links: [Github](#) page

Manual links: [Github](#) page

Tutorial links: some examples in the manual

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: None

HaploGrep

Associated with analyses: 11

Summary

HaploGrep provides a fully automated way to determine the haplogroup of mtDNA profiles. HaploGrep is implemented as a web application (available in a command line version, as well) based on Phylotree, a periodically updated classification tree estimated from data worldwide. Any given range of the mitochondrial genome can be used for haplogroup classification, which is based on the phylogenetic stability of mtDNA polymorphisms. For every input sample the top ten results and the phylogenetic position of the respective haplogroup are displayed, thus providing a detailed explanation how and why a haplogroup was ranked best. HaploGrep generates an interactive data visualization of the results and provides recommendations which polymorphisms should be analyzed additionally to get a more accurate result.

Input: VCF or FastA file (recommended) file

Output: Tables (Text) and Graphs (Graphviz DOT file).

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

--rsrs

By default HaploGrep expects that the data is aligned against rCRS. If the data are aligned against RSRS, add the --rsrs parameter.

--extend-report

For additional information on mtSNPs (e.g. found or remaining polymorphisms).

--hits

To export the best n hits for each sample. By default only the top hit is exported.

--lineage

Creates a graph of all input samples. The output is a Graphviz DOT file. [Graphviz](#) can be used to convert the dot file to a PDF file.

Download links: [Github](#) page

Manual links: [Github](#) page

Tutorial links: [HaploGrep](#) blog page

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [HAPLOFIND](#)

bcftools

Associated with analyses: 11 and 12

Summary

BCFtools is a set of utilities that manipulate variant calls in the Variant Call Format (VCF) and its binary counterpart BCF. Some of the bcftools utilities are VCF/BCF editing, concatenation, filtering, indexing, merging, and sorting, indel normalization, SNP calling, consensus sequence calling and generation of genotype likelihoods.

Input: VCF, bgzipped VCF and BCF

Output: VCF, bgzipped VCF and BCF

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

call

SNP/indel calling.

consensus

Create consensus sequence by applying VCF variants to a reference FastA file.

filter

Apply fixed-threshold filters.

index

Creates index for bgzip compressed VCF/BCF files for random access. CSI (coordinate-sorted index) is created by default. The CSI format supports indexing of chromosomes up to length 2^{31} .

merge

Merge multiple VCF/BCF files from non-overlapping sample sets to create one multi-sample file.

mpileup

Generate VCF/BCF containing genotype likelihoods for one or multiple BAM/CRAM files.

Download links: [htslib page](#)

Manual links: [bcftools page](#)

Tutorial links: Several examples are given in the manual.

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [VCFtools](#)

Yfitter

Associated with analyses: 12

Summary

Yfitter is an efficient dynamic programming algorithm that can assign haplogroups by maximum likelihood, and represent the uncertainty in assignment. Yfitter is a program for assigning Y chromosome haplogroups to individuals sequenced at low coverage. It is designed to be used in a samtools/bcftools pipeline (only with SAMtool version of 0.1.19, not greater).

Input: genotype likelihoods (qcall file generated using SAMtools/bcftools), a Y-chromosome tree file (xml file)

Output: Tables (Text) with haplogroup assignments.

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

This software tool is a script that needs the input to be fed using the *samtools* subcommands *view* and *mpileup*. The most important *samtools mpileup* parameter is:

`mpileup -C`

Adjust mapping quality.

It also needs as input the genotype likelihoods that are generated with *bcftools view* subcommand (not the most updated put the one that is part of SAMtool version 0.1.19, as the option of exporting the genotype likelihoods in qcall format is obsolete in updated versions).

`bcftools view -Q`

Output the QCALL likelihood format

Download links: [sourceforge](#)

Manual links: [sourceforge](#)

Tutorial links: Some examples are given in the manual.

Publication links: [arXiv](#)

Other similar software tools: [Yleaf](#), [Yhaplo](#)

READ

Associated with analyses: 13

Summary

READ is a method to infer the degree of relationship (up to second degree, i.e. nephew/niece-uncle/aunt, grandparent-grandchild or half-siblings) for a pair of low-coverage individuals. Applications which infer the degree of relationship based on modern-day DNA information typically require diploid genotype data. Low concentration of endogenous DNA, fragmentation and other post-mortem damage to ancient DNA (aDNA) makes the application of such tools unfeasible for most archaeological samples. READ uses a heuristic approach that can successfully infer up to second degree relationships with as little as 0.1x shotgun coverage per genome for pairs of individuals.

Input: TPED/TFAM files (generated via VCFtools using as input a VCF file).

Output: Tables (Text file) with kinship results.

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

This software tool is a script that needs the input to be fed using the *SAMtools* subcommand *mpileup*, the *bcftools* subcommand *call* and the *VCFtools* software tool.

The most important *SAMtools mpileup* parameter is:

`mpileup -q (-Q)`

Adjust base (or mapping; -Q) quality.

The most important *VCFtools* parameters are:

`--plink-tped`

Outputs (converts VCF to) TPED/TFAM files.

`--maf`

Sets threshold for minor allele frequency filter.

Download links: [bitbucket](#)

Manual links: [bitbucket page](#)

Tutorial links: Some information can be found in the manual.

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [grups](#)

BEAGLE

Associated with analyses: 14

Summary

BEAGLE is a state of the art software package for analysis of large-scale genetic data sets with hundreds of thousands of markers genotyped on thousands of samples. BEAGLE can a) phase genotype data (i.e. infer haplotypes) for unrelated individuals, parent-offspring pairs, and parent-offspring trios, b) infer sporadic missing genotype data, c) impute ungenotyped markers that have been genotyped in a reference panel, d) detect genetic regions that are homozygous-by-descent in an individual or identical-by-descent in pairs of individuals.

Input: VCF file, reference dataset/panel (e.g. HapMap) genetic map file

Output: options to export an image (PMG) or a coverage summary.

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

gprobs

Option to produce genotype probabilities.

niterations

It is a positive even integer giving the number of iterations of the phasing algorithm.

impute

Impute ungenotyped markers.

map

Input option for the reference panel genetic map file.

Download links: [BEAGLE page](#)

Manual links: [BEAGLE page](#)

Tutorial links: Several examples are given in the manual.

Publication links: [Cell](#), [ScienceDirect](#)

Other similar software tools: [IGV](#)

PLINK

Associated with analyses: 15 and 16

Summary

PLINK is a free, open-source whole genome association analysis toolset, designed to perform a range of basic, large-scale analyses in a computationally efficient manner. With PLINK, large data sets comprising hundreds of thousands of markers genotyped for thousands of individuals can be rapidly manipulated and analyzed in their entirety. As well as providing tools to make the basic analytic steps computationally efficient, PLINK also supports some novel approaches to whole-genome data that take advantage of whole-genome coverage. PLINK has five main domains of function: data management, summary statistics, population stratification, association analysis, and identity-by-descent estimation.

Input: PED/MAP files or TPED/TFAM files or BED/FAM/BIM files (all of them can be generated via VCFtools using a VCF file).

Output: A huge variety of output file options.

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

--snps

Select comma-delimited list of SNPs, allowing for ranges, e.g. snp1,snp2,snp6-snp12.

--keep

Keep only these individuals.

--make-bed

Make .bed, .fam and .bim.

--recode

Output new .ped and .map files.

--hardy

Report Hardy-Weinberg disequilibrium tests (exact).

Download links: [PLINK page](#)

Manual links: [PLINK page](#)

Tutorial links: Several examples can be found in the manual.

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [LAMPLINK](#)

EIGENSOFT

Associated with analyses: 16

Summary

The EIGENSOFT package combines functionality from the population genetics methods of Patterson et al. 2006 and the EIGENSTRAT stratification correction method of Price et al. 2006. The EIGENSTRAT method uses principal components analysis to explicitly model ancestry differences between cases and controls along continuous axes of variation; the resulting correction is specific to a candidate marker's variation in frequency across ancestral populations, minimizing spurious associations while maximizing power to detect true associations. The EIGENSOFT package has a built-in plotting script and supports multiple file formats and quantitative phenotypes. Here we are interested in the mergeit and the smartpca function. The mergeit program merges two data sets into a third, which has the union of the individuals and the intersection of the SNPs in the first two. smartpca runs Principal Components Analysis on input genotype data and outputs principal components (eigenvectors) and eigenvalues.

Input: PED or EIGENSTRAT or ANCESTRYMAP or PACKEDPED or PACKEDANCESTRYMAP files.

Output: Merged genotypes (one of the format as above) for mergeit. Tables (Text files) with eigenvalues and eigenvectors for smartPCA (these can be plotted).

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

-p

Uses as input a parameter file. In there the most important parameters for smartpca are:

lsqproject

PCA projections is carried out by solving least squares equations rather than an orthogonal projection step. This is appropriate if PCs are calculated using samples with little missing data.

Outliermode

Can be activated in order to remove outliers.

Download links: [Github](#) page

Manual links: [mergeit](#) page, [smartpca](#) page

Tutorial links: Examples can be found in the manuals. Some more info [here](#).

Publication links: [PubMed1](#), [PubMed2](#)

Other similar software tools: [PLINK](#)

ADMIXTURE

Associated with analyses: 15

Summary

ADMIXTURE is a software tool for maximum likelihood estimation of individual ancestries from multilocus SNP genotype datasets. It uses the same statistical model as STRUCTURE but calculates estimates much more rapidly using a fast, numerical optimization algorithm. Specifically, ADMIXTURE uses a block relaxation approach to alternately update allele frequency and ancestry fraction parameters. Each block update is handled by solving a large number of independent convex optimization problems, which are tackled using a fast, sequential quadratic programming algorithm. Convergence of the algorithm is accelerated using a novel quasi-Newton acceleration method.

Input: BED or PED, or EIGENSTRAT

Output: space-delimited files containing the parameter estimates (can be used to make plots).

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

-B

Outputs also the standard errors (calculated using bootstrapping) of the estimated parameters.

-j

Sets the number of threads used.

--haploid

Flag for haploid data.

-P

“Project” the new samples on to the population structure (allele frequencies) learned from the reference panels.

Download links: [ADMIXTURE page](#)

Manual links: [ADMIXTURE page](#)

Tutorial links: Several examples can be found in the manual.

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [Structure](#), [fastStrucstructure](#), [fineSTRUCTURE](#), [dys](#)

ADMIXtools

Associated with analyses: 16

Summary

ADMIXTOOLS is a software package that supports formal tests of whether admixture occurred, and makes it possible to infer admixture proportions and dates. The ADMIXTOOLS package implements 5 methods. The 3-population test, is a formal test of admixture and can provide clear evidence of admixture, even if the gene flow events occurred hundreds of generations ago. The F4 ratio estimation allows inference of the mixing proportions of an admixture event, even without access to accurate surrogates for the ancestral populations. The 4-population test, implemented as D-statistics, is also a formal test for admixture based on a four taxon 4 statistic, which can provide some information about the direction of gene flow. The qpBound test can be used for estimating bounds on the admixture proportions, given 3 populations (2 reference and one target). The rolloff test can be used for dating admixture events.

Input: PED or EIGENSTRAT or ANCESTRYMAP or PACKEDPED or PACKEDANCESTRYMAP files

Output: Table (Text file) with estimated parameters (these can be plotted).

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

-p

Uses as input a parameter file. In there the most important parameters are:

inbreed (for 3-population test)

Use if target pop is inbred OR (and crucially) if target is pseudo-diploid.

f4mode (for4-population test)

f4 statistics not D-stats are computed.

Download links: [Github page](#)

Manual links: The manuals of the five different functions can be found in the corresponding README files in the Github page.

Tutorial links: Examples can be found in the manuals.

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [Dsuite](#)

MAFFT

Associated with analyses: 17

Summary

MAFFT is a rapid multiple sequence alignment program that is designed to handle a huge (up to approximately 5,000 sequences) and long data (approximately 2,000 aa or approximately 5,000 nt) in a reasonable time on a standard desktop PC. It offers a range of multiple alignment methods, including the L-INS-i (accurate; for alignment of <~200 sequences), and the FFT-NS-2 (fast; for alignment of <~30,000 sequences).

Input: multiple unaligned sequences (FastA file)

Output: aligned sequences (FastA file).

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

--auto

Automatically selects an appropriate strategy from L-INS-i, FFT-NS-i and FFT-NS-2, according to data size.

--globalpair

All pairwise alignments are computed with the Needleman-Wunsch algorithm.

--localpair

All pairwise alignments are computed with the Smith-Waterman algorithm.

--genafpair

All pairwise alignments are computed with a local algorithm with the generalized affine gap cost (Altschul 1998).

--fastapair

All pairwise alignments are computed with FASTA (Pearson and Lipman 1988).

Download links: [MAFFT page](#)

Manual links: [MAFFT page](#)

Tutorial links: Several examples can be found in the manual.

Publication links: [PubMed1](#), [PubMed2](#)

Other similar software tools: [Clustal](#), [MUSCLE](#), other multiple sequence aligners [here](#)

***R*AxML**

Associated with analyses: 17

Summary

RAxML (Randomized Accelerated Maximum Likelihood) is a program for sequential and parallel Maximum Likelihood based inference of large phylogenetic trees. It can also be used for post analyses of sets of phylogenetic trees, analyses of alignments, and evolutionary placement of short reads.

Input: PHYLIP or FastA file

Output: Phylogenetic tree (Newick format).

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

-b

Specify an integer number (random seed) and turn on bootstrapping.

-d

Start ML optimization from random starting tree.

-l

A posteriori bootstopping analysis.

-m

Sets the model of Binary (Morphological), Nucleotide, Multi-State, or Amino Acid Substitution

-J

Compute majority rule consensus tree with "-J MR" or extended majority rule consensus tree with "-J MRE" or strict consensus tree with "-J STRICT".

-T

Specify the number of threads you want to run.

Download links: [Github page](#)

Manual links: [Github page](#)

Tutorial links: Detailed step-by-step examples are given in the manual.

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [ExaML](#), [PAML](#)

MALT

Associated with analyses: 18

Summary

MALT is a sequence alignment and analysis tool designed for processing high-throughput sequencing data, especially in the context of metagenomics. It is an extension of MEGAN6, the MEGenome Analyzer and is designed to provide the input for MEGAN6, but can also be used independently of MEGAN6. The core of the program is a sequence alignment engine that aligns DNA or protein sequences to a DNA or protein reference database in either BLASTN (DNA queries and DNA references), BLASTX (DNA queries and protein references) or BLASTP (protein queries and protein references) mode. The engine uses a banded-alignment algorithm with affine gap scores and BLOSUM substitution matrices (in the case of protein alignments). The program can compute both local alignments (Smith-Waterman) or semi-global alignments (in which reads are aligned end-to-end into reference sequences), the latter being more appropriate for aligning metagenomic reads to references.

Input: FastQ file

Output: RMA file (can be used as input in to MEGAN).

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

malt-build

Builds an index for the given reference database.

malt-run --alignmentType

Use this to specify the type of alignments to be performed.

malt-run --minPercentIdentity

Minimum percent identity.

malt-run --includeUnaligned

Use this to ensure that all unaligned queries are placed into the output RMA file.

Download links: [MALT page](#)

Manual links: [MALT page](#)

Tutorial links: Examples are given in the manual.

Publication links: [bioRxiv](#)

Other similar software tools: [Kraken](#)

MEGAN

Associated with analyses: 18

Summary

The aim of MEGAN is to provide a tool for studying the taxonomic content of a set of DNA reads, typically collected in a metagenomics project. In a preprocessing step, a sequence alignment of all reads against a suitable database of reference DNA or protein sequences must be performed to produce an input file for the program. MEGAN is suitable for DNA reads (metagenome data), RNA reads (metatranscriptome data), peptide sequences (metaproteomics data) and, using a suitable synonyms file that maps SILVA ids to taxon ids. At start-up, MEGAN first reads in the current NCBI taxonomy (consisting of over one million taxa). The main application of the program is to parse and analyze the result of an alignment of a set of reads against one or more reference databases, typically using BLASTN, BLASTX or BLASTP or similar tools including DIAMOND or MALT to compare against NCBI-NT, NCBI-NR or genome specific databases. The result of a such an analysis is an estimation of the taxonomical content (“species profile”) of the sample from which the reads were collected. The program uses a number of different algorithms to “place” reads into the taxonomy by assigning each read to a taxon at some level in the NCBI hierarchy, based on their hits to known sequences, as recorded in the alignment file.

Input: RMA file (generated by MALT)

Output: Options to export an image (PMG) or selected aligned reads (FastQ file).

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

This software tool is a visualizer. Thus, the command line can be used mostly to open the graphical user interface (GUI).

Download links: [MEGAN](#) page

Manual links: [MEGAN](#) page

Tutorial links: Examples are given in the manual.

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: [Kraken](#)

FastQScreen

Associated with analyses: 18

Summary

FastQ Screen is a simple application which allows you to search a large sequence dataset against a panel of different genomes to determine from where the sequences in your data originate. It was built as a QC check for sequencing pipelines but may also be useful in characterizing metagenomic samples. When running a sequencing pipeline it is useful to know that your sequencing runs contain the types of sequence they're supposed to. Your search libraries might contain the genomes of all of the organisms you work on, along with PhiX, Vectors or other contaminants commonly seen in sequencing experiments. Although the program wasn't built with any particular technology in mind it is probably only really suitable for processing short reads due to the use of either Bowtie, Bowtie2 or BWA as the searching application. The program generates both text and graphical output to inform you what proportion of your library was able to map, either uniquely or to more than one location, against each of your specified reference genomes. The user should therefore be able to identify a clean sequencing experiment in which the overwhelming majority of reads are probably derived from a single genomic origin.

Input: FAsTQ file

Output: Tables (Text) and graphs.

Most important command line subcommands / options (see the manual for the complete list)

--tag --filter

Generate a new FASTQ file in which each FASTQ read is tagged, listing to which genomes the read did, or did not align.

Download links: [Babraham](#) page

Manual links: [FastQ Screen](#) page

Tutorial links: [Youtube](#)

Publication links: [PubMed](#)

Other similar software tools: None

SECTION 2 – UNIVERSAL CHRONOLOGY SERVICE

1. Background & Highlights

E-RIHS Sub-Task 8.2.2 was envisioned as the feasibility study for the creation of a UCS, comprising all relevant techniques used to date heritage. These chronologies can be either numerical, incremental, or relative-associative-evaluative. Some dating methods used in HS may be better known than others as they are more extensively or routinely used in more widely studied scientific disciplines, such as the Geosciences, Archaeology and Conservation-Preservation Science, as opposed to others that are limited to a more exclusive array of HS disciplines such as Material Culture Science and Art Technological Research. As such, ¹⁴C, Dendrochronology and Luminescence are examples of extensively used dating methods in the former fields as opposed to Chromatography, Patination or Seriation in the latter disciplines.

The principal goal of UCS is to create a “one door to knock on” service that will help the user chose the most appropriate dating technique, laboratory and sampling method to its sample’s needs. Users may include museums, government and heritage-related organizations, art historians, archaeologists, paleoanthropologists, geologists, geochronologists, scientists, technicians, students, or simple individuals in need of chronologies. In turn, the expert service provided should be a combination of key provisions, strategic sampling, most appropriate dating method, expert advice, forgery analyses, and accurate dating.

1.1 Age Range & Overlap

The age range of HS is still not defined and is still debatable. If HS covers Tangible CH, Intangible CH, Underwater CH and NH, but also involves the Palaeontology and Palaeoanthropology communities, the age range has to cover the Anthropocene, Holocene and Pleistocene, i.e., at least the past 8-10 Ma to cover all HE and History, from modern to pre-historic times.

1.2 Dating Methods

An initial inventory of potential dating methods applicable to the majority of applications within the HS and their associated (geo) chronology laboratories within EU was carried out within the frame of this Sub-Task 8.2.2. The compilation of detailed information regarding each dating laboratory was achieved by extensive online inquiries, as well as requesting information from various experts and colleagues, besides tackling into the personal databases of this Sub-Task Leader.

The inventory of dating laboratories and experts encompasses the following information:

Dating Method	Techniques used or expertise within the specific dating field
Laboratory Name	Institution
Country	Institution Type (academic, governmental, private, etc.)
Email	Laboratory Leader, Head, Senior Expert, Senior Technician, main contact person
Postal Address	Observations and Details relevant

There are at least 44 dating methods that could be used in the multiple disciplines involving HS. Such methods go from precise numerical dating to relative-associative-evaluative approaches, and also involving incremental dating techniques. These dating methods are common to the various HS disciplines and other sciences such as Geology, Geochronology, Palaeontology and Palaeoanthropology.

The following table summarises and divides them in the 3 groups mentioned above. Each method falls into specific analytical categories, depending on the type of dating group.

Numerical Dating			Incremental Dating	Relative – Associative – Evaluative Dating						
Radiometric	Trapped Charge	Geochemical	Banded Records	Isotope Analysis	Decay (Profile) Analysis	Correlation	Forensic	Chemical Accumulation	Temperature-Affected	Soil Formation
Ar-Ar K-Ar	Luminescence: OSL TL	Thermochronology (Exhumation rates): U-Th / He	Archaeomagnetism Palaeomagnetism	207Pb-206Pb	137Cs	Archaeo-stratigraphy	Chromatography	Chemical Analysis (e.g. fluoride)	Amino Acid Racemization	Pedogenesis
Terrestrial Cosmogenic Nuclides (TCN)	Electron Spin Resonance (ESR)		Bivalve Sclero-chronology	88Sr-86Sr 87Sr-86Sr	210Pb	Bio-stratigraphy (index fossils, micro-fossils, pollen, etc.)	Gene Sequencing	Desert Varnish (cation ratio)	Obsidian Hydration	
Fission Track			Coral chronology	34S	32Si	Oxygen Isotope Chrono-stratigraphy	Ink	Patination		
14C (AMS)			Dendro-chronology	18O		Palaeontology	Seriation	Surface Weathering Features		
U-Series: U-Pb U-Th			Ice Core chronology	15N		Palaeosols				
			Lichenometry	13C		Stratigraphy (Geology)				
			Speleothem chronology	2H		Tephro-chronology				
			Varve chronology							

2.2 Survey Dissemination & Input

Due to the sheer amount of dating methods available with potential applications in HS (44), hence, the subsequent number of dating laboratories and experts in Europe alone, it was decided to substantially decrease this number to a workable survey group. Hence, only 8 different dating methods were chosen to participate in the survey, yielding the following number of European experts/laboratories contacted: 82 OSL; 4 TCN; 5 ESR; 12 Archaeomagnetism/Palaeomagnetism; 5 Dendrochronology; 5 U-Series; 50 Archaeometry; 60 ¹⁴C.

Of the questionnaires responded, the following results can summarise the level of input and overall participation of all 223 contacted experts/laboratories/institutions:

Questionnaire – Part I: 80 inputs were recorded; only 34 of those were completed surveys while 46 were incomplete.

Questionnaire – Part II: 60 inputs were recorded; only 19 of those were completed surveys.

The survey was open for responses from December 4th 2018 until June 15th 2019. A total of 140 questionnaires were received of which only 53 were fully completed to be included in the statistical analysis presented in this final report.

Part I of the survey dealt with general questions related to organisational and affiliation backgrounds, as well as general aspects related to the knowledge of E-RIHS and HS, and the intention for future participation if the UCS initiative becomes a reality. Below are the key questions related to the above.

The majority of the respondents work at a university (81%), while only a 16% work at a government facility and 2% at private (commercial) institutions.

- Main professional activity: 79% were Laboratory Heads, Directors or Leading Scientists; 15% were Experts or Scientists pertaining to the laboratory; 6% were Laboratory Managers, Head Technicians or Head Analysts; and 0% were the Centre's, Institute or Faculty Directors or Deans.
- General disciplines of academic affiliations: 6 Physics / Chemistry; 14 Geology / Geosciences / ES / EnvS; 10 Geochronology; 3 Humanities; 4 Archaeology / Physical Sciences / Museums; 1 Conservation / Restoration; 4 Archaeometry; 4 Engineering.
- Regional distribution in Europe: 1 Poland; 1 Belgium; 1 Israel; 1 Portugal; 1 Hungary; 1 Turkey; 2 Switzerland; 2 Germany; 2 Denmark; 3 Netherlands; 4 Italy; 4 Greece; 4 UK-Scotland; 4 Spain.
- Familiarity with E-RIHS initiative: 68% positive responses; 32% negative responses. Of those familiar with E-RIHS, 48% got to know the initiative through other colleagues while 35% of the participants are already involved in it or know about it through other ERICs such as IPERION, ARIADNE, etc.
- Familiarity with the field of HS: 94% gave positive responses and only 6% gave a negative one.
- Routinely date or characterise HS materials: 81% answered yes while only 19% responded no.
- Interest or consideration of dating or characterising HS materials: 100% positive responses. However, only 2 participants answered the type of materials they could date in the laboratory (insufficient to draw a viable answer).
- Interest in participating in the E-RIHS UCS initiative: 100% positive responses.
- Interest in QA&QC, e.g., homogenisation, normalisation, laboratory inter-comparisons: 91% responded with a yes while 9% answered no.
- Interest in becoming a member of E-RIHS's Scientific Assessment Committee that evaluates E-RIHS Research Proposals / Service: 88% answered yes while 12% responded no.

2.3 Survey Data & Key Results

The core of the survey is associated to Questionnaire Part II, which only a minority of participants filled out completely.

As the different 44 dating methods are divided in 3 main categories, one of the most important questions was related to the laboratory's type and expertise. Figures 1, 2 and 3 show the results corresponding to this question in the 3 main dating categories, respectively: Numerical Dating (Figure 1), Incremental Dating (Figure 2), and Relative – Associative – Evaluative Dating (Figure 3).

Figure 1. Number of laboratories with a numerical dating expertise.

Figure 2. Number of laboratories with an incremental dating expertise.

Figure 3. Number of laboratories with a relative dating expertise.

General field of expertise of the laboratory: 79% ES / EnvS / NH; 21% Palaeontology; 26% Palaeoanthropology; 90% Archaeology; 42% PH (building materials, construction, architecture; 47% CH; 11% others.

Does the laboratory perform authentication / certification / verification of archaeological and/or HS materials: 37% yes while 63% no. **Figure 4** gives an insight on percentage of materials authenticated (paintings, ivory samples, CH objects, wood artifacts, pottery, ceramics, wood, metals, organic materials), certified (archaeological materials) and verified (wooden painting supports, holy remains, paintings, ivory samples, CH objects, wood artifacts, CH artefacts, sculptures) based on type of materials.

Figure 4. Types of authentication, certification & verification based on materials

Generation of official certificates or authentication reports / seals: 21% answered yes, while 79% answered negatively.

Laboratory's years in service: see **Figure 5** for overall percentages depending on a time range.

Number of scientific publications produced by the laboratory over the past 10 years: 100% of laboratories answered positively. 68% of the publications were authored by the Lead Scientist or Laboratory's Director.

Number of technical reports (including dating results) produced by the laboratory over the past 10 years: 100% of laboratories answered positively. 53% of the publications were authored by the Lead Scientist or Laboratory's Director.

Figure 5. Number of years the laboratory has been in service.

All laboratories gave a feeling of the type of materials they handled and dated with most expertise. These varied extensively, including rocks, sediment, soils, minerals (quartz and feldspar), ceramic, pottery, wood, charcoal, teeth, organic materials (ivory, bone), metal, paint, textiles, fibres, mortar, paper, parchment, noble gases, elemental analyses. In terms of sites or dating localities, the wealth of the spread was substantial: from buildings, castles, churches of different cultural periods, to glaciers, caves, coastal areas, deserts and other environments. Sites were also related to museums when dealing with paintings, sculptures and other CH riches.

The majority of the laboratories deals with contained samples, cross-sections or cores, i.e., destructive samples. A few laboratories mentioned loose sediment or materials when asking about what type of sample is the most handled in the laboratory.

Openness and potential for a laboratory to date / characterise new materials and samples: 89% of the participants answered positively, while 11% were not interested.

Interestingly, 92% of the participants answered “commercial service” when asked which type of service is the most requested at your laboratory within any given year. 88% and 92% answered routine and experimental collaboration respectively. 87% selected calibration as well as maintenance of equipment as the other types of services most requested in the laboratory in any given year. No answers were associated to standardization procedures, laboratory inter-comparisons, or sample controls.

95% of the laboratories are self-sufficient, i.e., they have all the necessary facilities, equipment and personnel to perform a complete age determination and/or material characterisation, without contracting third-party laboratories or facilities for intermediate analyses. This is very important when ranking participating laboratories.

Time allocation of machine, technician and expert time is divided per activities. For half of the laboratories, 88% of the time is allocated to commercial dating, while the other half is allocated for research collaborations.

Potential number of new samples to allocate to E-RIHS UCS initiative: answers varied considerably among all laboratories and they were given in 3 ways. The minimum number of new samples a laboratory could handle would be 50 specimens, or 10% of its current capacity, or 2 weeks/year. The maximum number of new sampled could go up to 500 specimens, 50% of its current capacity or 50 days. The average number of new samples seems to be 200.

Laboratory personnel (averages): 86% are Staff Scientists from Professors to Head of Laboratory, all with permanent, full time positions; 88% are Staff Technicians either sample preparation technicians or analysts, all with full time, indefinite positions; 83% are Post-Docs with fixed-term, limited or temporary contracts; 83% are Graduate Students with limited contracts; 83% are Undergraduate Students.

In terms of *equipment capability*, all laboratories are equipped with state-of-the-art apparatuses, specific to each dating method and scientific field.

For 79% of the laboratories, all the specialised dating equipment is between 70-100% of capacity within any given year. The average commercial turn-around time for a sample at 83% of the laboratories is between 7 days (for fast dating methods, e.g., ¹⁴C) to 12 months (for slow dating methods, e.g., OSL). Turn-around seem to be the same if the sample is associated to research as well as experimental dating.

Notion of Access: Depending on the laboratory, samples can be a single item or a group of items. For 63% of the participants, samples are considered single items, whereas 37% of participants considered a sample to be a group of items. As such, 74% of the laboratories charge per single sample as opposed to 16% that charge per group of samples and 11% that charge per group of items.

89% of laboratories use SI units. 11% use other type of units.

63% of laboratories deal with quantitative results for intermediate results in the full spectrum of an age determination, whereas 26% of laboratories deal with both quantitative and qualitative results, as opposed to only 5% of laboratories that deal exclusively with qualitative intermediate results.

As for final dating results, the laboratory’s final dating report can fall into different categories (Figure 6), depending on the type of dating method.

Figure 6. Types of final dating results.

Multiple laboratories have very specific *sample collection rules*. These strictly depend on the dating technique and type of material to be dated. 89% of the participants request that E-RIHS UCS should strongly consider the two opposing views of sampling (to require an expert for sampling as opposed to not to) and allow for different access types to different facilities / laboratories, depending on the expertise and dating method. As such, **82% of the participants is in favour of providing access suggestions and regulations to E-RIHS UCS.**

In the same manner, shipping of samples can also be complicated or delicate. Nonetheless, 74% of participants considers that any shipping costs should be handled by the sender, whomever s/he might be. **Shipping costs should not be included in E-RIHS UCS access.**

None of the laboratories that participated in this questionnaire Part II consider that the laboratory should be located in the same location as the sampling or data collecting site. Nonetheless, 68% of participants do need to have/hold data from the area where the samples/materials were collected for comparative analyses or calibrations.

Is your laboratory ISO certified? **79% of laboratories are not QC or ISO certified.** Only 21% are (ISO 9001:2008 or ISO 9001:2015).

However, 84% of laboratories surveyed approves and encourages the development of the E-RIHS seal of quality (or its branding) as a form of prestige and certification. That said, 93% of laboratories are willing to participate in homogenisation, normalisation, and standardisation experiments and routines, as well as QC-QA inter-comparisons involving laboratories within the same dating domain, to improve and preserve the E-RIHS seal of quality.

Funding capacity and potential: the majority of the labs (79-88%) survive on both commercial service and consultancy income. 83% of the funds can also come from research grants. The rest of the funding is allocated through in-kind funds or philanthropic donations.

With this in mind, 68% of the laboratories surveyed is in favour of self-funding experiments, collaborations and research, envisioning E-RIHS UCS potential. Furthermore, 53% of the laboratories would be able to host 1 project per year, whereas 31% of laboratories would be able to host more than 1 project per year, and only 16% of the laboratories would be able to host 1 project every few years. The average amount of samples per project fluctuates between 20 to 500, depending on the dating method.

Membership and inclusion: 47% of laboratories surveyed find that in order for a laboratory to continue to be included in E-RIHS UCS, it would have to host more than 1 project per year. 32% of the laboratories surveyed think that having only 1 project per year is sufficient, whereas 21% believe that 1 project every few years is enough to be allowed continuity in E-RIHS UCS.

The survey results mirror a trend extensively seen in the academic and analytical service (laboratories) Worldwide: laboratories are eager to participate in novel research and front-line initiatives, but they restrain from sharing data or samples in fear of others taking advantage of results, data, etc.

2.4 Survey Barriers

A number of difficulties and issues were encountered since the creation of the survey. The main points are summarised below:

- Large number of dating methods: There are many dating methods applicable in HS. The same goes for their related laboratories and experts.
- Need to select the dating methods: There is a need to select which laboratories engaging in particular dating methods should have the highest level of response to efficiently completing the survey. This could help constraining the number of dating methods chosen to initiate the UCS at the upcoming E-RIHS.
- Unbalanced number of laboratories: There is a large number of laboratories for only a few particular dating methods and a very small number for the other majority of methods.
- Many contacted laboratories do not want to respond to simple questions regarding number of samples handled for different services (e.g. commercial, collaborative or internally driven research projects) and rough percentage breakdown, once they seem interested in participation.
- The purpose of the “what type of service” exercise is to demonstrate that most laboratories require multiple income streams to remain viable and for long-term survival. This can potentially affect productivity and collaboration endeavours.
 - Continuing with the 14C facilities exercise: only 5 laboratories answered these questions.
 - Many inquiries in other laboratories have gone unanswered, attesting to the difficulty of obtaining this kind or any other kind of information from chronology facilities.
- Many laboratories have a strict sense of exclusivity, “closed door” attitude and competition so they may not be open to be part of UCS, accept to promote our “Service” let alone collaboration.
- Most laboratories are under the umbrella of an institution that may have set rules for “service”, specifically thinking in relation to external services such as commercial work and even certain types of collaboration.
- Many laboratories may have backlogs (severe in some cases) which may be counteractive to the initiative and “service”.

2.5. Final Comments & Suggestions

Number of projects, number of samples, type of access and type of funding seem to be the most important yet questionable factors associated to becoming a member laboratory of E-RIHS UCS. A stronger general consensus on type of services and type of access is needed. Nonetheless, the overall impression towards this E-RIHS UCS initiative is very positive.

3. Recommendations: UCS Key Concepts to Define

Prior to the creation or during the initial stages of formation of E-RIHS, it is advisable to define some key concepts related to UCS. Clarification of these concepts would much improve the implementation and success of UCS. Some of these concepts are:

- The *age range* of HS is still not defined and is still debatable. What should be the lower and upper limits of HS time range?
 - Lower Limit: historical? Industrial Revolution? Anthropocene? 100 years ago? Yesterday?
 - Upper Limit: beginning of HE (i.e., 8-10 Ma) or only since the genus Homo appeared 2 Ma ago?
- Number of *dating methods* to include in the UCS:
 - Should all 44 dating methods summarised in this Sub-Task 8.2.2 be included in the UCS?
 - Most of them have related laboratories in Europe, but not all laboratories may want to be involved in E-RIHS.
 - All dating methods included in the UCS should overlap in terms of time range among techniques. These overlapping age ranges should be clearly defined.
- All the different options of the *service*, i.e., full in-house dating, partial in-house dating, dating with training of students/technicians, full dating analysis included, partial dating analysis (i.e., cheaper rates), etc.
- *Language proficiency*:
 - English as official language of communication at all levels, for all services, reports & documents.
 - Good knowledge of English should be obliged for participation at any level and in any type of service.
 - Reason: fast and effective communication should exist among all institutions / laboratories involved, back and forth with the main frame of E-RIHS. There should be no reason for miscommunication.
- Minimum and maximum number of *participating laboratories* per dating method and discipline:
 - Laboratories depend on several factors such as specialization of each lab, user demand and capacity to accept samples / services, number of personnel, geographical coverage.
 - There are laboratories specialized in a specific time range and type of material, which constrains the number of laboratories per dating method.
 - These issues are known to each individual laboratory and not necessarily to e.g. WP4.
- Number of *dating experts* involved per laboratory?
 - We need to start from the basis that an empty laboratory cannot be run by itself or offer services. Hence the importance of the experts involved in the initiative and the UCS process.
 - The amount of experts ensures the quality of both the service and the results.

Appendix A – UCS Online Survey: Questionnaire Part I (text)

Questionnaire Part I
Feasibility of Participation in E-RIHS
Programme: Universal Chronology Service (UCS)

General Laboratory Aspects

Name: _____
 Laboratory: _____
 Faculty / Field of Science: _____
 Institute / University / Centre: _____
 Location & Country: _____
 E-mail: _____

1. In which capacity are you filling out this questionnaire? *Please specify – chose one.*
 - Centre / Institute / Faculty Director or Dean: _____
 - Laboratory’s Head / Director / Leading Scientist: _____
 - Laboratory’s Scientist / Researcher / Expert: _____
 - Laboratory’s Manager / Head Technician / Head Analyst: _____
 - Laboratory’s Technician / Analyst: _____
 - Post-Doc / Research Fellow / Visiting Expert: _____
 - Graduate / Undergraduate Student: _____

2. Are you or were you already familiar with the **E-RIHS** initiative?
 - Y/N
 - **If yes**, since when? _____
 - Through which channels?
 - ✓ From other colleagues in the field
 - ✓ From your Centre / Institute / University
 - ✓ From conferences and meetings
 - ✓ From the news, website, Social Media
 - ✓ Others (please specify): _____

3. Are you and your laboratory familiar with the field of **Heritage Sciences**?
 - Y/N
 - **If yes**, do you routinely date and/or characterise Heritage Science materials?
 - ✓ Y/N
 - **If no**, would you and your laboratory be interested in becoming part of this field or consider dating / characterising materials related to Heritage Sciences?
 - ✓ Y/N
 - ✓ **If yes**, which type of materials could you date? Please specify:

 - ✓ **If no**, please provide a short explanation:

4. After reading the **E-RIHS Flyer enclosed in this Survey’s Introductory E-mail**, are you and your laboratory interested in participating in the **E-RIHS** initiative?
 - Y/N
 - **If yes**, please fill out the follow-up Questionnaire – Part II, for more detailed questions regarding your laboratory services and resources.
 - **If no**, please provide a short explanation:

5. Would you and your laboratory be willing to partake in any protocol homogenisation, normalisation experiments, laboratory inter-comparison initiatives promoted by **E-RIHS**, involving other laboratories within the same dating domain?
 - Y/N

6. Would you and your laboratory be willing to partake in quality control & quality management assessments, standardisation initiatives promoted by **E-RIHS**, involving other laboratories within similar dating domains?
 - Y/N

7. Would you, or an expert within your laboratory team, be willing to be considered for a probable / eventual Scientific Assessment Committee evaluating **E-RIHS** Research Proposals / Services or Access Requests related **exclusively** to **UCS**?
 - Y/N
 - **If not**, could you please provide the name of an expert you consider optimal for this position (outside your laboratory):

Appendix B – UCS Online Survey: Questionnaire Part II (text)

Questionnaire Part II
Feasibility of Participation in E-RIHS
Programme: Universal Chronology Service (UCS)

Laboratory Details, Type of Services, Resources, Access

This questionnaire is a **follow-up to Questionnaire – Part I**.

Here, specific details concerning your laboratory will be asked to gather as much and precise information concerning both the feasibility of creation of an **E-RIHS UCS** Programme and the potential for participation and involvement of your laboratory in such programme.

This questionnaire is meant for all potential laboratory participants that perform or are willing to perform scientific dating analyses on Heritage materials.

Please fill in as accurate as possible, rounding numbers as close as possible to reality.

Name: _____
 Laboratory: _____
 Faculty / Field of Science: _____
 Institute / University / Centre: _____
 Location & Country: _____
 E-mail: _____

8. In which **capacity** are you **filling out** this questionnaire? *Please specify – chose one.*

- Centre / Institute / Faculty Director or Dean: _____
- Laboratory's Head / Director / Leading Scientist: _____
- Laboratory's Scientist / Researcher / Expert: _____
- Laboratory's Manager / Head Technician / Head Analyst: _____
- Laboratory's Technician / Analyst: _____
- Post-Doc / Research Fellow / Visiting Expert: _____
- Graduate / Undergraduate Student: _____

9. **Dating Method & Technique.**

Please specify your laboratory's type and expertise.
Check all that apply.

- ✓ Numerical Dating (Direct Dating / Radiometric, Isotopic, Geochemical, Trapped Charge)
 - Ar-Ar, K-Ar
 - TCN
 - Tephrochronology – Fission Track
 - ¹⁴C
 - U-Series
 - Luminescence – OSL
 - Luminescence – TL
 - ESR
 - Thermo-chronology (U-Th / He or other)
 - Other(s): _____
- ✓ Incremental Dating (Direct Dating: Banded Records)
 - Archaeomagnetism
 - Palaeomagnetism
 - Bivalve Sclero-chronology
 - Coral Chronology
 - Dendrochronology
 - Ice Core Chronology
 - Lichenometry
 - Speleothem Chronology
 - Varve Chronology
 - Other(s): _____
- ✓ Relative – Associative – Evaluative Dating (Indirect Dating / Conservation)
 - Isotope Analysis (Pb, Sr, ³⁴S, ¹⁸O, ¹⁵N, ¹³C, ²H, etc.): *please specify* _____
 - Decay Analysis (¹³⁷Cs, ²¹⁰Pb, ³²Si): *please specify* _____
 - Archaeo-stratigraphy
 - Bio-stratigraphy (index fossils, micro-fossils, pollen, etc.)
 - Oxygen Isotope Chronostratigraphy
 - Palaeontology
 - Palaeosols
 - Stratigraphy (Geology)
 - Tephrochronology

- Chromatography
- DNA – Gene Sequencing
- Pigmentation (organic / inorganic) – Patination
- Painting Technique
- Seriation
- Desert Varnish (cation ratio)
- Surface Weathering Features
- Chemical Analyses (ICPMS, fluorine, ion beam, etc.): *please specify* _____
- Material Characterisation (x-Ray, XRF, XRD, Raman, etc.): *please specify* _____
- Microscopy (SEM, CT-Scan, etc.): *please specify* _____
- Amino Acid Racemisation
- Obsidian Hydration
- Pedogenesis
- Other(s): _____

10. General Field of Expertise.

When a **Dating Service** is requested in your laboratory, within which **field** does it fall into?

Check all that apply.

- Earth / Environmental Sciences / Natural Heritage
- Palaeontology
- Palaeo-anthropology
- Archaeology
- Physical Heritage (e.g. building materials, construction, architecture, etc.)
- Cultural Heritage (e.g., art, sculpture, painting, etc.)
- Other(s): _____

11. Number of Samples related to Heritage Sciences.

Based on the above, please provide an **approximate percentage of samples dated / characterised** in your laboratory **per field, within any given year**: which samples are from submitters (clients, collaborators, researchers, etc.) with a clear **Archaeological – Physical – Cultural Heritage background vs. a more palaeo-environmental** origin. *Please account for all that applies.*

Field	% Samples	Priority
Earth / Environmental Sciences / Natural Heritage		
Palaeontology		
Palaeo-anthropology		
Archaeology		
Physical Heritage		
Cultural Heritage		
Other(s)		

12. Authentication – Certification – Verification.

Do you and/or your laboratory authenticate / certify / verify archaeological- and/or Heritage-related materials?

- Y/N
- If yes**, please specify.
 - Authentication of: _____
 - Certification of: _____
 - Verification of: _____
- Do you provide **official certificates or authentication reports / seals**?
 - Y/N
- Please specify your **credentials** (e.g., national or international accredited, etc.):

13. Expertise Credentials - Experience.

Please specify your laboratory's **experience** related to dating / characterisation of materials.

How many **years** has your laboratory been in **service**?

Please account for all that applies.

- Laboratory established and running for:
 - < 5 years
 - 5 – 10 years
 - 10 – 15 years
 - 15 – 20 years
 - > 20 years
 - > 30 years
 - > 40 years
- Scientific Publications (including Open Files):
 - Number over the past 10 years: _____
 - Names of the top 4 authors & roles: _____
- Technical Reports (including final dating results):
 - Number over the past 10 years: _____
 - Names of the top 3 signees & roles: _____
- Authentications:

- Number over the past 10 years: _____
- Names of the top 2 authenticators & roles: _____

14. Expertise Specifics – Material Type Capability.

Please specify your laboratory's **expertise** in terms of type of **material(s)**, **site(s)** and **sample(s)**. *Please account for all that applies.*

- **Materials** (e.g., rock; block; sediment; soil; minerals; ceramic; metal; paint; wood; charcoal; paper; teeth; textiles; pollen; bone, etc.):
 - Most expert in: _____
 - Least expert in: _____
- **Sites** (e.g., caves; marshes; high altitude; underground; castles; churches; painting; sculpture, etc.):
 - Most expert in: _____
 - Least expert in: _____
- **Samples** (i.e., loose vs. contained sample; types of containers; sediment cores vs. hand specimens, etc.):
 - Most expert in: _____
 - Least expert in: _____

15. Potential for New Materials.

Would you be **open to** venture in dating / characterising **new materials** and **samples**?

- Y/N
- **If yes**, please specify. *Please account for all that applies.*
 - Most interested in: _____
 - Least interested in: _____
- **If no**, please provide a short explanation:

16. Types of Services.

Please provide the **Types of Services** requested to be done at your laboratory **within any given year**. Please detail % of samples accepted for each service and their priority within the laboratory's schedule. *Please account for all that applies.*

Type of Service	Y/N	% Samples	Priority
Commercial			
Routine Collaboration – Internal Research			
Experimental Collaboration – Internal Research			
National Laboratory QA Inter-comparisons / Standardizations			
International / EU Laboratory QA Inter-comparisons / Standardizations			
Calibrations / Verifications / Controls			
Maintenance / Mise à pointe			
Others			

17. Self-Sufficient Laboratory.

Does your laboratory (including Centre / Institution) have all the **necessary facilities, equipment** and **personnel** to perform a **complete** age determination and/or characterisation **from A to Z**? In other words, do you have a **self-sufficient / self-contained** laboratory with no need to reach out for **third-party analyses** to complete a dating procedure?

- Y/N
- **If no**, do you need to sub-contract other laboratories for specific intermediate analyses required for a complete age calculation / characterisation?
 - Y/N
 - **If yes:**
 - How many other laboratories do you use? _____
 - Are they QA-QC or ISO Certified facilities? Y / N / Doesn't know

18. General Time Allocation.

Please provide **amount (% or hours per year)** of **machine, technician, and expert time** allocated for the following activities. *Please account for all that applies.*

Activities	Machine(s) Time % or hrs?	Technician(s) Time % or hrs?	Expert(s) Time % or hrs?
Commercial			
Routine Collaboration – Internal Research			
Experimental Collaboration – Internal Research			
National Laboratory QA Inter-comparisons / Standardizations			
International / EU Laboratory QA Inter-comparisons / Standardizations			
Calibrations / Verifications / Controls			
Maintenance / Mise à pointe			
Others			

19. Potential Number of New Samples.

How much **machine time** would you consider or be able to eventually allocate to new samples submitted under **E-RIHS UCS Programme** within the framework of 1 year?

20. **Laboratory Personnel.**

Please provide the number of **personnel** engaged in any type of service / activity in your laboratory **within any given year**, their role, type and allocated time (part/full or give a %). *Please account for all that applies.*

Activities	Number	Role	Contract Type
Staff Scientists & Head of Laboratory			
Staff Technicians			
Post-Docs / Visiting Experts (on a regular basis)			
Graduate Students (M.A., M.Sc., Ph.D.)			
Undergraduate Students			
Others			

21. **Equipment Capability.**

Please describe the type of **equipment routinely** used for dating / characterisation in your laboratory.

Name / Brand: _____

Short Description: _____

Dating Technique most used for: _____

Dating Technique least used for: _____

22. **Equipment Capacity.**

In terms of equipment capacity, **how many** of the following does your laboratory have and what is their **estimated usage** within any given year.

Type of Equipment	Quantity	% Usage in 1 year
Specialised Dating Equipment		
Non-Specialised Dating Equipment		
Supplementary equipment needed to achieve an age calculation		

23. **Turn-around Times.**

For any given material / sample, what is the **average turn-around time** at your laboratory?

Please specify if the values given are in days, months or years.

Estimated Time	Commercial Service Dating <i>Days, Months, Years</i>	Research Dating <i>Days, Months, Years</i>	Experimental Dating <i>Days, Months, Years</i>
Best Time			
Average Time			
Worst Time			

24. **Notion of Access per Field of Expertise.**

In terms of “**Notion of Access**” and due to the very different ways of managing a laboratory, services and accesses, please answer the following based on your laboratory’s operational procedures. This will depend on whether your laboratory applies **Direct** (numerical and incremental) or **Indirect** (relative, associative, evaluative) **Dating Techniques**, and your major **Field of Expertise**.

- In your laboratory, is a sample treated as a single item or a group of items?
 - Single item / Group of items
- Do you charge per individual sample/item, group of items or group of samples?
 - Single sample / Group of items / Group of samples
- In your laboratory procedures, do you use SI units routinely?
 - Y/N
- Within the full spectrum of procedures required to complete an age determination / characterisation, are your intermediate results quantitative or qualitative?
 - Quantitative / Qualitative / Both / Neither
- In terms of Final Dating Results, in which of the following does your Final Report fall into:
 - A single number (quantitative value)
 - A range of “absolute” numerical values
 - A range of relative numerical values
 - A *terminus ante quem / post quem* approach
 - A minimum or maximum relative age approach
 - An interpretation of a qualitative assessment
 - A pass-fail approach

25. **Sample Collection Rules – Access.**

Depending on the Dating Technique and Laboratory, samples may be collected by any individual (expert or not) and sent directly to the lab, or require its assistance (expert) for retrieval of any given sample. Do you consider that **E-RIHS UCS** should strongly consider these two opposing views and allow for different access types to different facilities / laboratories, depending on the expertise and dating method?

- Y/N
- If **yes**, would you consider providing your access suggestions / regulations to **E-RIHS UCS** as an example?
 - Y/N

- **If no**, do you consider that all accesses to **E-RIHS UCS** should be handled the same way?
 - Y/N

26. **Sample Shipping Rules – Access.**

If a sample (only related to the **E-RIHS UCS** Programme) is to be shipped to your laboratory, in terms of shipping and handling costs, who should be paying for them?

- They should be included as part of the **E-RIHS UCS** access package.
- The sender, whoever s/he might be, at their own cost.
- The recipient laboratory, at their own cost.

27. **Laboratory & Data Location – Access.**

For several types of Dating Techniques, it is **imperative** for the laboratory to **be / operate in the vicinity** of the **research project, sample / material collection location**.

- Is that a requisite for your laboratory?
 - ✓ Y/N
- Do you need to have / hold data from the area where the sample / material were collected for comparative analyses or calibrations?
 - ✓ Y/N

28. **QA-QC & ISO Certification.**

Is your laboratory ISO certified?

- Y/N
- **If yes**, please specify. *Please check all that apply.*
 - ISO 9001:2008 or ISO 9001:2015
 - ISO 17025
 - ISO 45001
 - Other(s): _____
- **If no**, does your laboratory follow any specific quality control programme, protocol or organization initiative? Please specify:

29. **E-RIHS Seal of Quality – Brand.**

Would you encourage the development or be interested in the branding of **E-RIHS** as a sign/seal of quality, prestige and certification?

- Y/N
- **If yes**, would you be willing to participate in **homogenisation, normalisation, standardization experiments and routines, as well as QC-QA inter-comparisons** involving laboratories within the same dating domain, to improve and preserve **E-RIHS** quality?
 - Y/N
 - **If no**, please provide a short explanation:

30. **Funding Capacity.**

In general terms, please specify your laboratory's **general funding scheme**, i.e., how does your lab run, considering the following types of funding and to which percentage.

Types of Funding	Y/N	% Lab Funds
Commercial service income		
Consultancy		
Research funds (national and/or international grants)		
Industry contracts		
In-kind funds		
Private and/or philanthropic donations		
Regular Government input/income/contracts		
Core funding (internal)		
Other(s): <i>Please specify.</i>		

31. **Laboratory Funding Potential.**

Would your laboratory be able or willing to self-fund experiments, collaborations and/or research?

- Y/N
- **If yes**, please specify. *Please account for all that applies.*
 - 1 project every few years Maximum number of samples _____
 - 1 project per year Maximum number of samples _____
 - More than 1 project per year Maximum number of samples _____
- **If no**, please provide the minimum number of samples your laboratory could potentially date / characterise for free in a year. Please specify type of material/sample.

32. **Membership & Inclusion.**

What level of facility use would make worthwhile your laboratory's continued inclusion in **E-RIHS UCS**?

- ✓ 1 project every few years

Deliverable D 8.2

- ✓ 1 project per year
- ✓ More than 1 project per year

SECTION 3 – WORKFLOW IN DIGITAL ARCHAEOLOGY AND ANALYTICAL METHODS

The feasibility study concerns the analysis and the design of the pipeline from field data documentation to site/artefact analysis, and how this process is recorded, performed and shared in a common knowledge repository while integrating analytical and digital methods. Use scenarios will be developed together with major archaeological authorities and research labs promoting the collaboration between the public, research and private sector in HS.

Progress towards the definition of the workflow has been produced mainly by the subtask leader, and it was presented in international conferences and published in peer-reviewed conference proceedings:

- C. E. Catalano, V. Vassallo, S. Hermon, M. Spagnuolo (2018) “A Cultural Heritage Partonomy for the documentation of 3D digital artefacts of Cypriot coroplastic art”, *Proceedings CIDOC 2018 Conference*, Crete.
- Vassallo, V., **Hermon, S.**, Scalas, A., Mortara, and Spagnuolo, M., 2019. A re-evaluation of the concept of type in coroplastic studies based on 3D shape analysis of terracotta figurines from Ayia Irini, Cyprus. In *CAA 2019*.
- Scalas, A., Vassallo, V., Mortara, M., Spagnuolo, M. and **Hermon, S.**, An automatic approach for the classification of ancient clay statuettes based on heads features recognition, S. Rizvic and K. Rodriguez Echavarria (Eds). *EUROGRAPHICS Workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage 2019*, pp. 1–4.
- Scalas, A., Vassallo, V., Mortara, M., Spagnuolo, M., **Hermon, S.** 2018, Shape analysis techniques for the Ayia Irini case study, in R. Sablatnig and M. Wimmer (eds.) *The 16th EUROGRAPHICS Workshop on Graphics and Cultural Heritage*, the Eurographics Association, pp. 255-258.
- Vassallo, V., Sorrentino, G., Gasanova, S., **Hermon, S.** 2018, Integrating Analytical with Digital Data in Archaeology: Towards a Multidisciplinary Ontological Solution. The Salamis Terracotta Statues Case-Study, in M. Matsumoto and E. Uleberg (eds) *CAA2016: Oceans of Data Proceedings of the 44th Conference on Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology*. Oxford: Archaeopress, pp. 109-118.

Overall, the work done and in progress can be summarized as follows.

Archaeological multidisciplinary research relies on heterogeneous data types (measurements, spectra, etc.), while what is commonly published is the integrated interpretation of such data. A major task is to create a virtual environment where primary, processed and interpreted data are archived and available for interrogation. Such a task must rely on a knowledge management system that captures how data was acquired and produced (the scientific process of measurements, data acquisition, mathematical operations, etc.) along with its derived interpretation and reasoning process, ending with conclusions. This is essential for any scientific process where data transparency is the only mechanism for the verification of results, conclusions and duplication of experiments. The following block diagram exemplifies a characteristic workflow integrating digital archaeology and analytical methods.

Digital workflow

Vassallo, V. 2016. A 3D digital approach to study, analyse and (re)interpret Cultural Heritage: the case study of Ayia Irini (Cyprus and Sweden). Campana S., Scopigno, R., Carpentiero G., and Cirillo M. (eds.), Archeopress.
 Vassallo, V. 2017. The archaeological collection of Ayia Irini (Cyprus). A 3D digital approach to analyse and reinterpret a 20th century study. Ancient Cyprus, an unexpected journey. Communities in Continuity and Transition. Bombardieri L., Amadio M. and Dolcetti F. (eds.), Artemide: Roma.

Figure 1. A characteristic workflow integrating digital archaeology and analytical methods.

Crucial steps are capturing and motivating the choices made when choosing a particular digital documentation method over the other along the data transformation path (from data to interpretation and knowledge) as well as choosing the most suitable spatial digital contextualization of the work done (e.g. GIS, virtual reality, etc.), followed by the semantic integration of such multi-source and heterogenous data (the left side of the diagram). The right side of the diagram details some of the data gathered during a typical archaeological investigation process.

In this context, CIDOC-CRM, and its particular the CRM_{dig} are important to mention, since the latter is an extension particularly develop to represent the process of capturing processes typical to digital archaeology. It is based on the definition of digital events and digital things, as follows:

Figure 3. Diagram of CRM classes and properties

The process of creating the digital objects is described in CRM as a machine driven event, activated by a human actor:

Figure 4. Process of creating the digital objects

The post-processing of digital data can be described as follows

Figure 5. Post-processing of digital data

For example, 3D data on the geometry of objects can be captured by various methods (passive or active sensors) and using different instrumentation and processing software, each however with their limitations and constraints (see image below for two 3D data acquisition methods, based on laser scanning and photogrammetry respectively). Correctly capturing these processes and semantically representing them in CIDOC-CRM, according to the above-described diagrams enables more accurate investigations of the stored data, conduct complex queries and enable an accurate estimate of data quality, based on formally describing its provenance.

Figure 6. Integration of 3D models and textures

Once 3D data is acquired, several measurements and observations can be performed, in order to gather insights on how objects have been manufactured, their preservation state and possible classification. Complex shape analyses, such as those exemplified below, may hint on the possible standardization of production of, in this case, of terracotta figurines, patterns of production and related quality of manufacture. For examples, algorithms analyzing face features may be used for clustering them according to their technique of manufacture, mould (left) versus handmade (right):

Figure 7. Face analysis algorithm

Such analyses can be semantically represented through the CIDOC-CRM_{dig} extension, by using the following path:

Figure 8. CIDOC CRM representation of face analysis algorithm

Archaeological documentation relies as well as legacy data, which can take many forms, such as museum collections of artefacts acquired tens of years ago and thus having outdated artefacts description, excavation diaries or old articles. The image below is an example of data belonging to a same archaeological site, its findings being split between various museums, and its early reports and excavation diaries not being published anywhere, but archived.

Figure 9. Extracting information

A possible solution to extract valuable data from such sources is to map various data formats using CIDOC-CRM ontology as the unifying underlayer within a comprehensive integrated digital environment (see below). Information embedded in old diaries and reports can be processed using methods deriving from natural language processing and thus identify potentially valuable information that can be further on structured again with the help of CIDOC-CRM.

Another integration example along the workflow of archaeological analysis regards spatial analysis, as well as integration of legacy data with newly processed data. Such data can be spatially investigated through complex statistical analyses as well as scientific visualization, as shown in the image below, where old data is geo-spatially aligned with existing situation.

3D reconstruction of the excavation and of the structures

Calculation of the heights' levels

Figure 10. Workflow of archaeological spatial analysis

In this example, old drawings of stratigraphic features are geo-spatially located and corroborated with other excavation data, such as distribution and extension of walls, in order to check inconsistencies in the spatial distribution of finds and consequent stratigraphic considerations.

Finally, the proposed solution is to go towards a description through a common/global extensible schema represented by a formal ontology that guarantees 'integration without loss of meaning', represented by the possibility to allow data publication in a semantic format, through mappings between archaeological resources and the CIDOC-CRM ontology, in order to implement archaeological interoperability at conceptual level. The definition of mappings to CIDOC-CRM allows to capture the semantic richness of our data and give the possibility to express their variety of information by the means of the classes and relations of the CIDOC-CRM and its extensions. Data integration through a CIDOC-CRM description will guarantee to view information in a unified way. This would make explicit all the informative layers in order to be queried (and successively interpreted) as if they were accessible all at once. The image below exemplifies the integration between digital and analytical data, where legacy data, XRF measurements, ethnographic studies and 3D shape analyses are semantically represented with CIDOC-CRM_{sci+dig} extensions.

Semantic integration of multidisciplinary data

Figure 11. Integration between digital and analytical data

The related CIDOC-CRM block diagram is represented below:

Figure 12. CIDOC CRM diagram for the integration between digital and analytical data

We describe here the part of the mapping related to the results of physico-chemical analyses as production of a scientific observation and the parameters of such analysis. The study is a sequence of events described within CRMsci: the scientific analysis (S4_Observation) is performed with a certain instrument (E22_Man_made_object) set with specific parameters (E54_Dimension). Revising CRMsci, it results that there is lack of a property for the specification of the instruments' settings. For this reason, we propose the introduction of a property "Ox_Use_Specific_Parameters", to be borrowed from the CRMdig extension (L13_used parameters) and adapted to the scientific description.¹⁶ The scientific observation is performed on some points or features (S15_Observable entity) located on a specific place (E53_Place) on the object (E22_Man_made_object). The analysis (S4_Observation) provides measurements (E54_Dimension) that in case of physico-chemical analyses having a certain concentration (E16_Measurement) with own measurement units (E58_Measurement_Unit).

All the steps of the digitisation process, from data acquisition to visualization, and the digital analysis, are described using CRMdig.¹⁷ The integration of archaeological description and the digital description is done through the item (E22_Man_made_object) that is composed of (P46_is_composed_of) a certain material (E18_Physical_thing). E18_Physical_thing becomes a D1_Digital_Object through D2_Digitization_process, operated with a D8_Digital_Device. The final step consists of the integration of all the extensions in order to describe the concepts of our research and their publication online in a holistic way.

To sum up, integrating analytical and digital data within an archaeological workflow is based on two CIDOC-CRM extensions:

CIDOC-CRMsci, intended to integrate and facilitate the management, integration, mediation, interchange and access of metadata resulting from various scientific and analytical observations (e.g. biodiversity, geology, geography, archaeology, cultural heritage conservation). It can be an appropriate tool to register the scientific activity and its process.

CIDOC-CRMdig encodes metadata about the steps and methods of production ('provenance') of digitisation products and digital representations such as 2D and 3D data created by various technologies (all steps and parameters from data capture down to the end-user outcome).

Open questions to be addressed in the future are: refinement of CRMsci and related metadata schema for the description of analytical measurements; a more detailed description of the decision-making process when acquiring data (paradata); the reasoning process implemented during the analysis of collected data through measurements and observations in order to get knowledge inferred from the axioms and assertions in the ontology and its individuals, linking to other archaeological data sets under CIDOC- CRM (and a possible publication at the Linked Open Data).

SECTION 4 – REFERENCE COLLECTIONS

1. Rationale

Rigorous application of Heritage Science relies for a large part on reliable, repeatable and interchangeable instrumental analyses. If the same or similar analytical techniques are used in different labs, research institutes and universities, some sort of quality control is needed to assess the degree to which data can be compared and exchanged. One way doing that is by using standard materials with known properties that are made generally available. Another is to use round-robin testing, where test materials of (potentially) unknown properties are split and distributed among the testing facilities. Comparison of the measurement outcomes indicates to what extent data of the various institutes can be compared and interchanged. Standard samples and round-robin testing are common in various analytical branches of industry and e.g. environmental research and isotope labs.

In order for reference and test materials to be suitable for heritage science research analyses, their composition or other measured properties need to be in similar ranges as the heritage materials investigated. As modern reference materials are geared towards modern materials, most – if not all – of the available samples and round-robin test schemes are not suitable for the heritage field.

In subproject 8.2.4., we investigated to what extent to what extent reference and test materials may be produced for use in the field of heritage.

2. Actions

A visit by DJH to the offices of WEPAL (a Dutch institute that runs a round-robin test facility in soil and environmental research) made clear that the logistics of producing round-robin test materials and of gathering and analysing the required data must not be underestimated.

We composed and distributed a questionnaire to all ERIHS ERIC members that (1) perform scientific analyses on heritage materials or (2) that have (physical or digital) collections that may be made available as reference collections and/or as source for reference of source materials. The questionnaire inventoried (1) wishes and demands with regards to specific materials, samples etc. as reference materials or for round-robin testing with (potential) consortium members and (2) collections that are present with (potential) consortium members that may be available for one or more of the following:

- (1) as reference dataset
- (2) as digital reference database
- (3) to be digitized to contribute to reference database
- (4) as source for samples for reference collections
- (5) as source for samples for round-robin testing

The questionnaire was sent to 148 email addresses from 66 institutes in 26 countries.

3. Results

Reactions to the questionnaire was limited, with only 8 of the potential partners reacting. A large number of different analytical techniques (see table 1)

Table 1 Results of questionnaire. Frequency of available techniques.

Method(s)	Frequency
XRF ,pXRF	6
FTIR, p-FTIR	6
Raman	6
XRD (incl. Rietveld)	5
TGA/DTG	5
Raman microscopy	2
VIS-NIR multispectral analyses	2
IFM (immunofluorescence microscopy)	1
Enzyme-Linked Immuno-Sorbent Assays (ELISA)	1
HPLC	2
(Py)GC-MS	2
IC	2
ICP-MS, ICP-OES, HR-ICP-MS	2
X-Ray Radiology	2
CT and micro CT	5
SEM, SEM-EDX	6
Thermal Dilatometry	1
Optical microscoppy incl. polarization and thin section studies	4
IEC	1
Climatic and win tunnel experiments	1
Optical coherence tomography	1
Micro-profilometry	1
DRMS	1
Ultrasound	1
IRR_reflectography	1
Photography	1
Grain-size analyses	1
Confocal laser microscopy	1
Apparent Electrical conductivity (ECa)	1
AFM	1
Contact Angle (wettability) & capillarity/permeability	1
Palaeomagnetism/magnetic susceptibility	3
14C, MICADAS	2
Dendrochronology	2
OSL	2
ESR	1
U-seris dating	1

From table 1 it is clear that even this small proportion (c. 20%) of potential ERIHS participants provide an impressive range of techniques. It is also clear that some of the techniques, especially the material composition analyses (XRF, XRD etc.) are in use in a large proportion of the facilities, which would make standards, reference materials and round-robin testing feasible.

Unfortunately, very few materials were available that could be used for such reference and test materials: Most collections that are available only allow non-destructive and minimal invasive techniques. Based on the limited availability of suitable materials, further testing was deemed not possible.

4. Outlook

Reference and test materials could still play an important role in quality control and interoperability within ERIHS ERIC. We have, unfortunately, not been able to test the logistical and statistical challenges that are involved with this due to lack of suitable testing materials. For a next phase, it would be of prime importance to gather, source or make either original or replica heritage materials that are suitable as standards, as reference materials or for round-robin tests.

SECTION 5 INTEGRATION OF SCIENTIFIC DATA WITH GENERAL HERITAGE DOCUMENTATION

The integration of scientific data with general heritage documentation requires the preliminary definition of a common ontology to create a knowledge base including the analytical data and the other documentation, consisting in texts, images, drawings, 3D models and so on. Moreover, controlled vocabularies are also required to standardize the use of terms.

The high-level design of the knowledge graph is illustrated below.

Figure 1. Diagram of the knowledge graph

The boxes indicate the main classes to be used for the description, and the arrows the connecting properties. The resulting ontology is compliant with the CIDOC-CRM ontology, the standard for cultural heritage. It uses some of its classes, denoted with E. It also uses classes from CRMdig, denoted with D, and from PEM, the PARTHENOS Entity Model, denoted with PE. For the sake of simplicity, the relationships indicated in the figure are not fully described, but they also correspond to properties of the CRM or of its extensions.

Explaining the above in words, a scientific **Dataset** is produced by a scientific **Activity**, i.e. a measurement, which is part of an analysis campaign, also an Activity, on an artefact (**Human-made Object**), for example a painting, a statue, etc. This Activity takes place at some **Place** and during a **Time**. The Activity is carried out by an **Actor** (or more), belonging to some institution (**Legal Body**) and uses a specific **Device**.

Further specifications are also necessary. For example, the Device has a general Type, e.g. an XRF analyzer, and several specific types, e.g. the make and the model. The Activity includes preliminary activities such as the device calibration. The measurement can involve only a part of the artefact, i.e. a Sample. Different measurement methods may require slightly different metadata for their characterization. All such details have been analyzed in detail for the most common techniques and are fully described in the papers referenced below.

It appeared to be necessary to describe and standardize the protocols used for the analyses, including the equipment and the software used to manage them and to process the raw data produced during the experiments. At present, such standards appear to lack for most of the analyses and equipment, so it has been decided to proceed in the design task putting this information into a Note and postpone such complete descriptions to later. In the meanwhile, they will be indicated with a short reference such as, for instance, the commercial name of the equipment and the reference to external documentation for the protocol.

As far as controlled vocabularies are concerned, the preliminary study has ascertained that they do not exist for the scientific part, or – in some cases – there are partial vocabularies mostly based on current practices but not organized, for example, in SKOS. They exist, instead, for the text description.

An internal report on these vocabularies has been produced, in which various name lists are considered for the different categories of analyses. This report concerns the structure of the reference terms, (standard notations, gazetteers, PIDs, URIs, URLs, etc.) such as the following:

- **Actors and Artefacts:** VIAF/ORCID, DBPedia URIs, authority files, controlled lists of institution/person names
- **Time Spans and Periods:** ISO8601 encoding, `xsd:Date/xsd:DateTime` formats, PeriodO URIs (*period names and time spans*)
- **Places:** WGS84 (*spatial coordinates*), Geonames URIs (*places identification*), Pleiades/Pelagios URIs/URLs (*historical places*)
- **Persistent Identifiers:** unambiguous, permanent entities identification
- **Thesauri, vocabularies,** controlled lists of **types:** e.g. AAT (*Getty's Art and Architecture Thesaurus*), Nomisma.org (*numismatics*), PICO (*Italian ICCD thesaurus*)

At present, some the most common analytical techniques have been considered. They include: XRD, XRF, C14 dating, microscopy, multispectral analysis.

Further details on the complete ontology have been published in [5], [6], [7], [8].

In conclusion, this approach enables the interoperability of a repository of analytical data with a document repository also based on the CRM, which is the objective of this task.

As regards the implementation, a high-level design has been proposed for the system, illustrated in the following picture from the user's perspective.

Figure 2. Working in a VRE

The system, named DIGILAB, enables researchers to work in a Virtual Research Environment where they can access data from different sources, all interoperable with each other as they are based on compatible ontologies, all based on the CRM. In this vision, a researcher searches for data in “local” repositories aggregated in a common metadata catalog. They contain both text documents or images and the numeric results of scientific analyses with the experiment metadata. The outcome is further refined, so that eventually only the relevant results are retained in the VRE. This is cloud-based, so other researchers may collaborate on working on them. Post-processing services are also available in the VRE, for example concerning image enhancements or the synthesis of numeric sets in spectra. The desired combined result is then produced.

The high-level design of such integrated system has been described in Niccolucci *et al* (2017), Felicetti and Niccolucci (2018), Castelli *et al* (2018, 2019).

The DIGILAB detail design and implementation was **not** part of the present task 8.2.5. However, it was the natural destination of the preparatory work made here. Also, it could indicate specific requirements to be added to the design summarized above. In sum, without DIGILAB the present work risks to remain an academic exercise and has never been tested on real data.

DIGILAB could re-use methods and tools already available and requiring only a modest adaptation. Moreover, its implementation would have required limited resources because of the offer by another project to provide a similar system and to collaborate in any required adjustment. Additionally, services (for example, dedicated text mining) were successfully developed within other EOSC-related projects and might have been included in DIGILAB.

The high-level design produced by this Task was used by one of the partners, KIK-IRPA, for the project of their own repository and data management system, named HESCIDA, which was successfully submitted to the Belgian government, approved and funded, and is currently in the implementation stage.

Nevertheless, the technical development of E-RIHS DIGILAB was stopped at some point, as the people designated to be in charge of it did not produce the design, let alone any implementation plan. Thus, nothing has happened beyond the design produced by the present Task. It has never been possible to test the metadata design and the ontology.

The work done here is being continued in other projects such as EOSCpillar, where the problem is addressed using text mining and linking texts to scientific results stored in database that implements there the DIGILAB; and in ARIADNEplus, which embeds this approach in a large-scale cloud-based system aggregating archaeological data.

The research carried out in this task has been published in peer-reviewed journals and presented at international conferences.

References for Section 5

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SECTION 6 – ADVANCED MATERIALS FOR RESTORATION

Remedial and preventive conservation is a fundamental step for the valorization and conservation of cultural heritage. For that reason, a large number of research groups are active worldwide in this field. It is of paramount importance to create and/or facilitate new routes that allow a complete exploitation of new ideas up to reach high TRL solutions. This means that several stakeholders and end-users may benefit by the Research Infrastructure activity.

The feasibility study is aimed at the designing an integrated pipeline involving different analytical tools and innovative materials for the definition of the best conservation procedures to ensure the best practice and maximum efficiency for the beneficiary community. Unfortunately, the very limited resources, i.e. the small number of person/months assigned to our institution, did not allow the full achievement of the expected results.

Figure 1. An example of the cleaning gels developed in the H2020 project NANORESTART. (Center and bottom rows) Some of the masterpieces cleaned using the gels: paintings by Jackson Pollock (“Alchemy”, “Two”, Peggy Guggenheim, Venice), Pablo Picasso (“The Studio – L’Atelier”, Peggy Guggenheim, Venice), and Roy Lichtenstein (“Whaam!”, Tate Modern, London).*

* Image from the ECHOES Position Paper, https://www.echc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/Position-Paper-FP9_RM_revised_low.pdf

The foreseen activity has been mainly developed in the framework of the European cluster ECHOES, led by CSGI and created under the auspices of the EC. This cluster connects all the projects, funded within the H2020 programme, finalized to the development of new materials and solutions for CH conservation (e.g. NANORESTART, NANOCATHEDRAL, APACHE, NEMOSINE, and INNOVACONCRETE).

The cluster started an open discussion about the best way to provide new services to private and public museums, libraries, archaeological areas, conservation institutes, in the field of material science. A survey of the demand for new solutions provided clear evidences about the potentiality of research activities in this area. The interaction between ECHOES and the European infrastructure E-RIHS can be pursued in the future, in order to integrate new services to the RI.

The emerging needs reside, in particular, in the conservation of multicomponent art materials, which are of interests for several different community (e.g. paleo-anthropology, archaeology, conservation, social science and humanities, and others), mainly because the conventional conservation methods are often not usable; for that, such artefacts are constantly under menace of irreversible degradation. A large demand is coming from these 'areas', especially from museums that are facing completely new degradation processes and are looking for new solutions.